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Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Executive Summary

The EU-Funded AURORA project will empower 7,000 people across the social spectrum to deliver substantial carbon emission reductions. Five communities (four from universities and one from a rural municipality) will become citizen science hubs that will deliver reductions in carbon and costs for heating, lighting and transport. The project will provide an app for participants to monitor their energy behaviours and receive personal advice on reducing energy demands. As 'citizen scientists', these communities will use crowd-funded photovoltaic facilities to show how to install ca. 1 megawatt in total of renewable energy in their communities. Successful participants will become ambassadors for change and the findings will be shared with global citizen science communities.

This is a public deliverable that reports on the creation and exploitation of local energy facilities at the different local energy communities. The local energy communities were established in 5 distinct locations across Europe: Denmark (Aarhus University), United Kingdom (Forest of Dean District Council), Portugal (University of Évora), Slovenia (University of Ljubljana) and Spain (Technical University of Madrid).

All Work Package 3 beneficiaries encountered more or less severe unpredicted obstacles. Significant efforts were made by partners to overcome these obstacles, which mostly arise from communication and collaboration with third parties, university administrations and legal limitations. These barriers required significant amount of time and effort to overcome, which delayed the project execution, required project extension, and in two demonstrators required to completely change the initial business plans.

However, thanks to all the barriers, we have developed different approaches to Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) That can be summarized in three classes:

- REC as a new independent cooperative
- REC under existing legal entity
- Virtual REC

Barriers in most demonstrators also required that the social community is legally separated from the installation.

In Aarhus, the REC Universitetets Energisællesskab F.M.B.A (UEF) was established as a new independent cooperative and crowdfunded the PV installation that in part provides electricity to Aarhus University. REC under existing legal entity was established in Madrid and in The Forest of Dean. In Madrid, the informal UPM community, the Campus Sur Platform, worked together with external energy advisor Ecooo to crowdfund a PV facility on a nearby private primary school, which is legally organized as a cooperative. In the Forest of Dean District council, the formal community benefit society, the Forest Community Energy together with existing cooperative Big Solar Co-op crowdfunded PV facilities on the local swimming pool and on the local school. Virtual energy communities were established in Ljubljana and Evora. In Ljubljana, the community Student Energy Club lead the process of installation of PV power plant, which was funded by the University of Ljubljana. In Evora, the community Sustainable Action Group leveraged an existing PV installation.

Monitoring systems were established at PV facilities with data being gathered and displayed in the Aurora Energy Tracker App. Two communities already replicated the approach under existing legal entity, while there are several more communities in close contact to replicate other approaches as well.

This deliverable links to the Work Package 3 – Upgrading Social Communities to Local Energy Communities and is a direct result of the work done in Task 3.4 – Local Energy Infrastructure, Open Monitoring and Round Robin Characterization.

Policy Summary

The task of developing Renewable Energies Communities (REC) based on photovoltaic power plants (PVPPs) on or including the Universities turned out to be very demanding. Most of the encountered barriers are related to various policies that regulate the procedures required to establish, fund and lead the REC. The obvious albeit idealistic idea of the Aurora project that the universities, as the institutions that foster research, innovation and progressive thinking, should be in the core of REC made their creation even more difficult if not impossible. There are various factors affecting this.

The first difficulty is that all required policies governing legal requirements are scattered in several different laws. This makes this problem very complex as it is difficult to find someone that possesses the knowledge of all these laws and is willing to support such problems. Additionally, different government ministries overlook different fields and this may lead to legislation incompatibility.

Renewable energy community is most often represented by the legal structure of cooperative. The **cooperative** requires all partners to have equal managing power. This is a strong barrier, as universities' administrations were not keen on participating in such a legal form with equal rights, while having higher risk. The only demonstrator that pursued the approach via a new independent cooperative and include the university was the team at Aarhus University – but even there, the University was not a part of REC, but rather only a stakeholder, who bought the electricity produced by the REC's PVPP. The REC itself was established independently by the members of AU team and other enthusiasts. It must also be noted, that this was possible in Denmark due to the unique “prosumer via third party” framework only available in Denmark.

Legal forms of **association** and **foundation** were explored in Evora and Madrid, but they were both unable to form the REC using them. The first attempt of REC via General Foundation of the UPM, was discarded because universities are public institutions and do not fall under local authorities or private sectors in legislation. Second attempt of new ad-hoc foundation among UPM and their members was discarded because European Commission's mandate to optimize public sector dictated that there should be only one foundation per institution. In Evora they also tried to pursue either association or foundation approach, but their attempt was discarded because the government in the past ordered the closure of foundations detained by universities and the University of Évora had to close its own foundation. The process for the creation of an association would be lengthy and bureaucratic, and it would not be granted the direct sale of PV energy to the University due to public procurement law.

The University of Évora itself is therefore implementing a **collective self-consumption** with its own buildings, sharing energy through the grid. These PV facilities are funded with the environmental funds that AURORA team in Évora supported the University throughout the application process. Another possibility that was explored, was the possibility of the University to instate a crowdfunding process and distribute financial benefits to participants, however this was not possible because the financial activity is outside of the scope of a university. This forced the team in Évora to pursue a **virtual approach** to energy community, similar to the University of Ljubljana.

At the University of Ljubljana, creation of new legal entity was blocked by legal dispute about legal subjectivity between universities and faculties. Therefore, a **virtual approach** was adopted, where community members are connected via an informal entity called Student Energy Club that acts as an intermediate step towards creation of crowdfunded RECs. The powerplants were funded by the University and provide economic and environmental benefit to the University in effectively a self-consumption scheme, while they are providing demonstration benefit and a possibility for virtual investment to the community members via the Aurora Energy Tracker App.

The final approach in Madrid and the approach in the Forest of Dean is within **external cooperative**. In this approach they both found already existing cooperatives and ran all the procedures under their coverage. In Madrid they did this

via the local school Colegio Centro Cultural Palomeras (CCCP), which is a cooperative. However, the private investors that crowdfunded the installation did this by providing a loan to the cooperative and not by entering into cooperative's ownership structure. The whole project was done with the help of another external company (legally a cooperative) that deals with consulting, investments and installation of PV power plants. In the Forest of Dean, they have setup the demonstrator via an external cooperative, which is already established in the business of RECs by crowdfunding and installing the PV power plants.

In addition to finding a correct legal form for the REC, income tax complicates REC establishment. When a person invests in REC one does so with the intention of generating renewable energy to offset his energy consumption and with economic interest to get economic returns. However, as soon as one is to receive any financial benefit, it is subject to tax. While tax is essential for society, initial implementation and yearly reporting to tax offices presents significant effort and raises operating cost of RECs, making micro investments less attractive and economically unfeasible. Tax exemption for small investments in RECs would make REC establishment easier.

While developing our demonstrators, most of the teams noted that administrations bodies are not keen to take legal risk and venture into the unknown field of RECs. While this is understandable from the personal point of view of employees, it also makes it significantly more difficult if not impossible for research teams and also possible replicators to establish RECs. This shows that the reward for mitigating climate change is not large enough to incentive REC establishment compared to relatively small (financial) gains. This could be improved by two things, one is better education with raised awareness of the problem, while the other is legislation that would require and encourage adoptions of RECs on universities and other public institutions.

The obstacles encountered by the demonstrator sites are explained in respective introduction chapters of section 3 of this document.

The overall findings of the project on policy related matters are gathered together, explained and discussed in detail in the paper published in Solar RRL:

- A.B. Cristóbal et al., "Igniting University Communities: Building Strategies that Empower an Energy Transition through Solar Energy Communities," Solar RRL, vol. 7, no. 24, p. 2300498, 2023, doi: 10.1002/solr.202300498.

Replicator Summary

During the course of the Aurora project we embarked on the establishment of five Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) based on photovoltaic power plant (PVPPs) that would be crowdfunded and established on four universities and in one municipality in Europe. The straightforward implementation using the universities as the establishing parties of the RECs proved to be impossible. Therefore, we developed several other concepts that fulfil the goal of raising awareness about climate change, energy production by photovoltaics and offsetting carbon emissions by using photovoltaics. Each concept is adapted to local legislation and social acceptance in different countries.

The developed approaches are summarized in three classes:

- REC as a new independent cooperative
- REC under existing legal entity
- Virtual REC

and further explained. Replication limitations are addressed in the introductory sub-section 6.1. Two communities already replicated the Aurora approach, described in sub-section 6.6, while replications in progress are described in sub-section 6.7.

To enable replication, all establishment procedures are documented in the following subsections of this document:

- 3.1 Demonstrator Site – Madrid, Spain, page 14:
 - Establishment of a crowdfunded REC with help of external company and a nearby School Colegio Centro Cultural Palomeras with PV installation and two heat pumps on the school building
- 3.2 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, page 23:
 - Establishment of a virtual energy community based around current PV power plants installed in the university which will be complemented with new PV power plants and registered under a collective self-consumption EC
- 3.3 Demonstrator Site – Ljubljana, Slovenia, page 32:
 - Establishment of a virtual energy community based around the PV power plant installed on the roofs of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering
- 3.4 Demonstrator Site – Aarhus, Denmark, page 52:
 - Establishment of a crowdfunded REC as a cooperative with PV installation on the buildings rented by the university
- 3.5 Demonstrator Site – Forest of Dean, United Kingdom, page 61:
 - Establishment of a crowdfunded REC through national crowdfunding organization for PV with PV installation on municipality's leisure centre and school

Although not successfully realized, an approach to establish REC under the coverage of the Red Cross was developed in Évora that has replication potential, while it also addresses the topic of energy poverty and justice:

- 3.2 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, page 23:
 - Establishment of an energy community based on PV power plants installed on the Red Cross buildings addressing energy poverty.

Finally, while the goal of the Aurora project was to build photovoltaic power plants, the approaches developed by the demo sites can also be replicated with different types of power plants depending on the energy source available at given location.

A chapter on Replication is available in section 6 of this document (Aurora project, deliverable 3.3).

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1 Introduction

In the beginning of the AURORA project, WP3 beneficiaries produced individual business plans for creating renewable energy communities and installing demonstration photovoltaic power plants (PVPP). Business plans considered the peculiarities of distinct locations, universities, and existing communities to provide tailored solutions. This was described in detail in D3.1.

Partners with demonstrators, namely, UPM, UEvora, UL, AU and FoDDC followed the proposed business plans aiming to establish energy communities and install demonstrating PVPP according to the predicted schedule. In the process, all partners experienced different unpredicted obstacles that caused delays in the proposed implementations. The obstacles arose mostly from communication and collaboration with third parties, university administrations and due to legal and structural limitations. Partners invested significant efforts and produced various innovative solutions to overcome these obstacles. Despite the best efforts the process required considerable time investment that cumulatively led to the delay in implementation at all partners.

This final version of the deliverable D3.3 is based on D3.2 *Report on the creation and exploitation of local energy facilities*. It reports in detail on the endeavours of project partners. It describes the encountered obstacles and developed mitigation measures or workarounds.

The structure of the document is as follows.

In section 2, a short summary about the legal framework proposed by the EU, its implementation in different countries and the implication for the AURORA project are given.

In section 3, local renewable energy communities and their photovoltaic facilities are described per each demonstrator site. For each demonstrator, the background circumstances for the establishment of renewable energy communities are described as they have important implications in the implementation of local facilities. Then, the chapters may vary, but in general they present the conceptual design of the demonstrator PV facility, followed by the actual implementation. The implementation chapter describes encountered obstacles and mitigation measures that led to the successful realization of the demo sites. Depending on the demonstrator, there may be more chapters, including the failed approaches. The failed approaches do not only present important lessons learned, but also present possible opportunities for replications. This is followed by a description of local dissemination and communication actions and an explanation how the demonstrator will operate after the end of the Aurora project. Each subsection is finalised with a summary and a conclusion.

In general, approaches developed can be grouped in three classes, implementation of which is then described in detail in corresponding chapters of this deliverable

- REC as a new independent cooperative
 - Section 3.4 Demonstrator Site – Aarhus, Denmark, page 52:
Establishment of a crowdfunded REC as a cooperative Universitetets Energisfællesskab F.M.B.A (UEF) with the PV installation on the buildings rented by the university
- REC under existing legal entity
 - Section 3.1 Demonstrator Site – Madrid, Spain, page 14:
Establishment of an informal community Campus Sur Platform, which organized crowdfunding and PV power plant installation, together with external advisor, under legal coverage of an existing cooperative operating a nearby school
 - Section 3.5 Demonstrator Site – Forest of Dean, United Kingdom, page 61:
Establishment of a formal community benefit society, the Forest Community Energy, which organized crowdfunding and PV power plant installation with the help and under legal coverage of an existing national cooperative Big Solar Co-op

- Section 3.2 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, subsection 3.2.3 Red-Cross approach, page 25: Establishment of an informal community Sustainable Action Group, which tried to organize crowdfunding and PV power plant installation under legal coverage and on the buildings of local Red Cross delegation – a failed attempt
- Virtual REC
 - Section 3.3 Demonstrator Site – Ljubljana, Slovenia, page 32: Establishment of a virtual energy community Student Energy Club (SEK) based around the PV power plant installed on the roofs of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering
 - Section 3.2 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, subsection 3.2.5 Virtual approach, page 29: Establishment of an informal community Sustainable Action Group and leverage an existing power plant for demonstration purposes

In section 4, monitoring, surveillance and operation assessment actions are described and explained. Firstly, a general document with technical specification prepared by QPV is described. Individualised versions, customised by some demonstrator sites, of this document were used for public procurement. Secondly, power plant production study is explained in detail. Production studies will be used to evaluate the performance of installed power plants. The section is finalised by a chapter on the monitoring system, where monitoring systems installed at all different locations are presented.

In section 5 a round robin is designed where different PV technologies will be evaluated in terms of degradation, ageing and energy yield in different locations.

Section 6 delves into the replication opportunities of the approaches developed by the Aurora project.

Section 7 outlines the dissemination and communication activities focused on WP3.

The deliverable is rounded up by a concluding chapter.

2 Framework

This section gives the reader major comprehension on some points of the Directives and legal framework of energy communities that we described in D3.1 - Report on the business models to follow-up by the different local energy communities. The implementation of these directives in participating countries plays an important role in decision making by the partners, and is therefore also crucial to understand the barriers, with which the demonstrators are dealing.

Energy communities are associations of individuals, households, or businesses that come together to produce, consume, and share energy in a collaborative and sustainable manner. These communities are based on the idea of transitioning towards a decentralized and participatory energy system, as opposed to the traditional centralized model controlled by large energy companies.

In an energy community, participants can generate energy from renewable sources such as solar panels, wind turbines, or biomass systems. This energy can be used to meet the needs of the community members, and any surplus can be sold to the electrical grid or shared among the members.

One of the main goals of energy communities is to promote the production and local consumption of renewable energy, thereby reducing dependence on non-renewable energy sources and decreasing greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, they foster citizen participation and collective decision-making regarding energy, empowering community members and fostering a greater sense of responsibility and environmental awareness.

The principles of these communities are regulated by two European directives that define two types of energy communities. The Renewable Energy Directive EU 2018/2001 sets the framework for "renewable energy communities" (RECs), while the Internal Electricity Market Directive EU 2019/944 introduces roles and responsibilities for "citizen energy communities" (CECs). Both types of communities can engage in similar activities, including energy generation, distribution, supply, aggregation, consumption, sharing, storage, and provision of energy-related services. The differences between them are minimal, but for the purpose of AURORA, which aims to become energy communities as citizen science hubs, adopting a REC seems most appropriate. RECs specifically target local individuals, where "effective control must rest with members that are in proximity to the projects owned and developed by the community." CECs, on the other hand, do not have such restrictions. But in the UK demo, their model is open to the investment of citizens outside of the Forest of Dean in order to maximize the power capacity of the installations and reduce risks for investors.

The legal form in which energy communities can be structured is variable, such as cooperatives, associations, foundations, etc., if the principles of democracy and proportionality among the members, as outlined in the European directives, are fulfilled.

It is worth noting that although the European Directives were promulgated in 2018 and 2019, and Member States were expected to adopt the Directives before the 30th of June 2021, there are still many EU countries without a national legal framework for energy communities. This situation ultimately leads to doubts and hesitations among local stakeholders. Therefore, business models were adjusted to comply just with the actions permitted by national law.

In Spain, these directives were not yet passed into the national legislation.

In Portugal, the renewable energy directive 2018/2001/EU (REDII) has been adapted under the Portuguese decree no 15/2022 of January 15th to promote and facilitate the self-consumption of energy and the Renewable Energy Communities, creating conditions for the establishment of innovative economic and social solutions benefiting of new technological opportunities. In December 2024, a new Portuguese decree law was published – DL no 99/2024 of December 3th, which partially transposes RED III directive. In terms of REC, it allows the possibility of doubling the

distance in which energy sharing can occur in the context of REC or Collective Self-Consumption for low density regions.

In Denmark, there have been citizen-initiated energy cooperatives since decades ago, providing examples on how energy communities can be organized there. Additionally, RECs were inserted in the Law on the Promotion of Renewables in 2021. With additional provisions that are implemented in the net settlement executive order and the instant settlement executive order, as well as an executive order on renewable energy self-consumers, which entered into force on 1 January 2023, it has become possible to set up an energy community that self-consumes through a third party, which is the model adopted in the demonstration site at AU.

In Slovenia, the EU 2019/944 Directive was implemented in the Slovenian Electricity Supply Act (ZOEE), where RECs are only briefly mentioned and they further rely on the older Cooperatives Act (ZZad).

In the UK, the deadline for transposition of the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001/EU (REDII) into national law was after the UK's withdrawal from the EU and at present, RED II has not been transposed into UK law. Current policy and regulation in respect of RED II and the Internal Electricity Market Directive EU 2019/944 is derived from retained EU law and UK statute. In addition, although the UK has been released from the renewable energy targets under RED II following Brexit, the UK-EU Trade and Cooperation Agreement includes a commitment to promote the use of energy from renewable sources and reaffirmation of the EU's 2030 targets.

Specific manifestations of the general EU legal framework are described in detail for each demonstrator site in the corresponding introductory subsections in the following section.

3 Local energy solar facilities

Within the AURORA project, five demonstrator local energy solar facilities will be installed at project partners:

- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid – UPM
- Universidad de Evora – UE
- Aarhus Universitat – AU
- University of Ljubljana – UL
- Forest of Dean District Council – FoDDC

The demonstrators are planned across Europe to showcase PV in different environments (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Locations of AURORA local demonstrators

Each local facility is planned to have a power of about 200 kW. The local facilities will be used for demonstration purposes, to present PV and to offer first-hand experience of operating and owning a PV facility. Each facility is planning to use different module technologies to display them to renewable energy community members, as well as to investigate the performance of different technologies in different climates and mounting positions. The production of each power plant will be visible in the premises of the partner for demonstration purposes.

3.1 Demonstrator Site – Madrid, Spain

3.1.1 Introduction

Although Spain has not passed the RECs Directive yet, there are currently hundreds of REC initiatives in Spain. Many are supported by grants such as the CE OFICINAS Program for granting Community Transformation Offices for the promotion and revitalization of energy communities or the IMPLEMENTA Program for granting singular projects of energy communities, both promoted by the Institute for Energy Diversification and Savings (IDAE) from Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO). Basically, they are fitting in the national law for collective self-consumption. This limits the actions that a REC can perform but as for the project objectives is what we are looking for.

Thus, at the beginning of the project, the AURORA coordination team in Madrid proposed the constitution of a Renewable Energy Community (REC) under the legal form of a Foundation, integrating the REC into the General Foundation of the UPM (FGUPM). This was the most suitable option analysed with the lawyers hired. This model fitted with the interests of the University while ensuring participant's rights. The members of the REC would be students, professors, and administrative staff from the Campus-Sur of the UPM (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid) and the UPM itself.

In this model, UPM would carry out a management assignment to the FGUPM for the constitution and development of the REC, allowing the FGUPM to use the rooftops of the Campus-Sur buildings to install a 200 kW PV power plant.

The PV facility would be financed by economic contributions (micro-investments) made by students, professors, and administrative staff. Then, UPM would receive electricity generated by the REC facilities and would pay the REC based on the electricity bill savings achieved.

However, once this proposal was presented to the UPM decision-making body and after a long period of discussion, the UPM Rectorate refused the proposal, under the argument of lack of regulation in Spain related to the constitution and operation of Renewable Energy Communities. Moreover, the electricity sector regulation (Electricity Law 24/2013 approved on 26 December 2013) defines the Renewable Energy Communities in article 6 as *“legal entities based on open and voluntary participation, autonomous and effectively controlled by partners or members that are located in the vicinity of the renewable energy projects that are owned and developed by the legal entities themselves, whose partners or members are natural persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities.”* The UPM Rector argues that universities and their Foundations are not included in the list of possible members of a REC (universities and linked foundations are not *local authorities*), so this would also justify the refusal to constitute a REC. We have to say that until this decision came, we presented several modifications of the business model so each new version was adapted to solve hesitations and doubts arisen in the Rector team and passed to us.

From the point of view of the project, an ad-hoc Foundation among the university and their members would constitute a local entity that can be understood as a local authority, so it should be eligible to participate in RECs (Renewable Energy Community). But it is worth noting that the idea of constituting an ad-hoc foundation was radically discarded. Some years ago, there was a general mandate from the European Commission to optimize the structure of the public administration by reducing the number of foundations linked to public bodies and the general rule of thumb is to accommodate new actions in the current foundations.

Despite these arguments, in order to overcome the barriers perceived by the UPM Rectorate, the project team presented to the UPM decision-making body a second proposal in which no formal energy community would be constituted, but UPM would carry out a management assignment to the FGUPM to install a 200 kW self-consumption PV power plant on the rooftops of the Campus-Sur buildings that would be financed by the micro-investments made by students, professors, and administrative staff. These investors would act as a bank giving money to the General Foundation. The investment can take the form of participatory savings accounts or loans. Just to give participants the rights linked to a legal structure, this could be joined into an association where decisions can be adopted democratically.

Investments provided by the individual micro-investors would be repaid by UPM energy savings provided by the self-consumed energy from the 200 kW PV facility. In this way, the micro-investors would have an economic return for the investment made.

This second model was also refused by the UPM General Foundation, and then, by the UPM heads.

As a consequence of this result, the original project has been completely modified and a new approach has been implemented: The Renewable Energy Community was established informally as a Campus Sur Platform by members of the UPM Campus-Sur community (students, professors and administrative staff). The goal of the REC is the promotion and execution of renewable energy projects in educational centres in the Community of Madrid.

A first project has been selected in a primary school located one km away from UPM Campus-Sur, the so-called Colegio Centro Cultural Palomeras (hereinafter referred to as CCCP). It is a private school, which is formally established as a cooperative. This cooperative will be the legal vehicle for crowdfunding. The school operates in a public building, whose owner is IVIMA, a public body of the Community of Madrid.

Apart from these considerations, the AURORA coordination team in Madrid has carried out an intensive awareness-raising campaign within the Campus-Sur university community involving students, professors and administrative staff, reaching the engagement of 275 persons, who are willing to participate in the project and invest a total amount of €150,000. Students, however, have shown more interest in participating in workshops and obtaining credits (ECTS) than in making micro-investments.

Figure 2: Different awareness-raising activities in Campus-Sur (Madrid)

3.1.2 Conceptual design

3.1.2.1 Location

The CCCP primary school is located in the South-East of Madrid in the Puente de Vallecas District, just one km away from UPM Campus-Sur. Figure 3 shows the CCCP and the Campus-Sur locations.

Figure 3: CCCP and Campus-Sur Locations. (Source: Google Maps)

The PV power plant was installed on the roof of the school building, as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4: 42.3 kW PV generator proposal on CCCP school building

The potential capacity of this rooftop is 57 kW, but the power capacity has been sized to 42.3 kW after the assessment of the energy consumption profile of the school for one year taking into account the energy consumption of the planned 26 and 39 kW heat pumps.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036418.

3.1.2.2 Installation details

The selection of the rooftops for the PV facilities has been done considering the following criteria:

- Shade-free rooftops.
- Proximity to low voltage electrical connection points.
- PV generators are installed in a way that maximizes energy production.
- Representative technologies present in the PV market.
- Potential for research and teaching activities.

Currently, the Solar Energy Institute (IES-UPM) in Campus-Sur operates two monofacial PV generators with traditional technology (Si-p, multicrystalline, BSF cells) and a bifacial generator with more advanced technology (Si-n, monocrystalline, PERC cells). Therefore, to achieve a representative sample of PV technologies with the CCCP project, the following PV generators were installed:

- 34.2 kW with Tunnel Oxide Passivated Contact (TOPCon) cells.
- 8.1 kW Hetero Junction Technology (HJT) cells.

3.1.3 Implementation

Due to the reasons exposed in the introduction, the PV facilities at the UPM premises could not be implemented in a crowd-funded way proposed by Aurora. The implementation was therefore done at the CCCP school.

Considering the cumulated delay in the project, UPM team has contracted the Spanish company Ecooo (<https://ecooo.es>) to support the project in the process of setting up the cooperative, as well as in the identification and implementation of renewable energy projects. Ecooo also promotes the crowdfunding campaign, manages income from investors and subsequent amortization, carries out engineering and project execution, and signs a contract with CCCP for PV system and heat pump installation.

The first successful step was to get the approval from the CCCP representatives. The next legal milestones was the permission to install the PV system from IVIMA (public body owner of the building). This was more difficult to achieve, but it was obtained on May 5th.

After successfully securing the legal background between the stakeholders, we launched the crowdfunding. As previously discussed the Madrid demonstrator as the first project of the Campus Sur Platform operates within an existing cooperative – the CCCP school. This is a legal and operational necessity, to enable financial flows which we could not have been achieved via the UPM. In terms of citizen participation, only existing cooperative members are involved in decision-making. The new crowdfunding participants are giving a loan to the cooperative, and are therefore “only” financial backers without governance roles.

The crowdfunding campaign was launched with a target of €150,000. Thanks to all preceding communication, awareness-raising and preparational activities, 161 investors have quickly participated in crowdfunding achieving a total of €118,350 of investment. Investors come from the CCCP members, the Campus Sur UPM community and the network of Ecooo. The actual budget for the PV and heat pumps projects was €137,940, and the difference was provided by the CCCP.

The demonstrator facility includes 1 self-consumption PV system with 42.3 kW power and 2 heat pumps for two buildings (39 and 26 kW). The PV installation has been completed on July 14 2025. The first heat pump was installed in parallel with the PV installation, while the second one followed shortly after in July 2025.

3.1.4 Timeline

The timeline of the UPM demonstrator is as follows:

		Previous	abr-24	may-24	jun-24	jul-24	ago-24	sep-24	oct-24	nov-24	dic-24	ene-25	feb-25	mar-25	abr-25	may-25	jun-25	jul-25	
1	Constitution of the REC																		
1.2	ECOOO consultant contract																		
1.3	Constitution of the Campus Sur Platform																		
1.4	Elaboration of documents, regulations and contracts																		
1.5	Documents approval																		
1.6	Launch of the CCCP initiative																		
2	Information, Awareness and communication campaig																		
2.1	Office opening																		
2.2	Displays to communicate AURORA																		
2.3	Edition and placement roll-up posters, banners, brochures, and others																		
2.4	Creation and launch of the local AURORA website																		
2.5	Dissemination of newsletters and technical texts																		
2.6	Participation in the 20 different Departments Council meetings																		
2.7	Meetings with the four researching centres and the library staff																		
2.8	Meetings with the four student delegations																		
2.9	Development of a communication plan within the IDEATON project with students																		
2.10	Participation in events organized by students																		
3	Crowdfunding and support in the constitution of the REC																		
3.1	Design of the CF campaig																		
3.2	Launch of crowdfunding campaign																		
3.3	Subscription management																		
4	Local Energy Infrastructure, Open Monitoring and Characterization																		
4.1	Final PV power plant design and heat pumps sizing																		
4.2	Request of offers for supply and installation																		
4.3	Quality control																		
4.4	Installation phase																		
4.5	Commissioning																		

Table 1: Timeline of the demonstrator at CCCP

3.1.5 Local dissemination and communication

In late 2022, UPM undertook an extensive effort to organize meetings and discussions with all members of Campus Sur regarding the crowdfunded installation. We hosted 12 ad-hoc events to inform about the installation with 140 participants and also provided online webinars for those who could not attend in person. The objective of these sessions was to introduce the concept of the energy community and gauge the interest of our community. Through these physical and online meetings, combined with our communication campaign, we received 275 letters of interest, indicating that approximately €140,000 to €150,000 could be raised to crowdfund the installations.

From these meetings, we concluded that while there is significant interest in the concept the extensive educational work required should not be underestimated. The community's low level of knowledge about the operation of the facilities, surplus management, the legal attributions of an energy community, and the implications of being part of a cooperative—either as a cooperative member or as an account participant—highlights the need for thorough education and awareness-building efforts.

Figure 5: Photos from the end of 2022 events.

As the installation project progressed and reached its final definition, a meeting was organized on April 16, 2024, to present the crowdfunded installation project to the school families. Over 70 people attended, and once again, it was evident that although the community is very enthusiastic about the idea, significant doubts remain. This meeting followed a series of discussions with all the school's faculty and alumni representatives to analyse whether the project aligned with their needs.

Figure 6: Photos from the engagement events at the school.

At the same time, the first two meetings (held on April 24 and May 24) have already taken place at Campus Sur to establish the Campus Sur Platform. These meetings have involved around 15 UPM individuals who expressed interest in being part of its core group, focusing primarily on addressing the legal questions related to becoming a member rather than just an account participant.

Figure 7: Photo from the cooperative members meeting on the 24th of May.

The execution of the communication and dissemination plan carried out by Ecooo, has been developed with the following citizen participation actions:

1. Press Releases Sent to Media Outlets

Two press releases were sent to journalists via the Odoos platform, with the aim of raising awareness about the project's progress and its social impact:

- 5 December 2024
- 10 December 2024

Title of the press release: *“More than 300 children in Vallecas bid farewell to extreme temperatures at their school.”*

These communications aimed to highlight the tangible benefits of the project and its positive impact on the school community for national media, as reflected in the media coverage.

2. Communications to Individuals Interested in Financing (via Odoos)

Several communications were sent to individuals who had participated in or expressed interest in the citizen financing of the project, keeping them informed about the campaign's progress and milestones achieved:

- 12 December 2024: *“First milestone of Project Aurora achieved! Thank you for your participation.”*
- 11 March 2025: *“Final stretch of Project Aurora: Help us give it one last push!”*
- 1 April 2025: *“Final stretch of Project Aurora: Help us give it one last push!”*
- 27 June 2025: *“Project Aurora becomes a reality: Construction starts NOW!”*

These communications helped maintain the commitment and engagement of the funders throughout each phase of the project.

3. Mailings to the University Community (UPM) and the Palomeras Cultural Centre School

To raise awareness of the project and promote collective investment, monthly mailings were sent between January and April 2025 to:

- The university community of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)
- Families and staff of the CCCP
- Individuals who had previously shown interest in investing before the official launch

Mailing dates:

- January 2025
- February 2025
- March 2025
- April 2025

These mailings helped expand the project's social base and build a support network committed to its goals.

4. Results of the Citizen Financing Campaign

- Total completed forms: 164 individuals
- Total contracts effectively paid: 161 individuals
- Total amount raised: €118,350
- Note: Some of these individuals may have contributed €100, changing their status from “unpaid” to “paid”
- Information requests received (via form and email): 15 enquiries

This citizen mobilisation has been key to the project's viability, demonstrating civil society's interest and commitment to initiatives that promote sustainability, energy efficiency, and child well-being – starting from the neighbourhood of Vallecas, the UPM, and the Ecooo Energía Ciudadana community.

3.1.6 Operation after the end of the project

The agreement between the CCCP school and UPM Campus-Sur community, with the support of Ecooo, will include an operation and maintenance (O&M) period equivalent to the shares' repayment period (15 years). During this time, O&M actions will be carried out to ensure the quality of the system and its proper functioning. At the end of this period, the facility will be handed over to the school, which will continue to self-consume photovoltaic energy until the end of the system's lifetime, i.e. 25 years.

3.1.7 Identified replication opportunities

Up to now, other projects have been identified by the Campus-Sur REC:

- **UPM new Campus-Sur Hall of residence.**

UPM is building a hall of residence on the grounds of Campus-Sur. A link has been made between the AURORA and the project developer to develop a community energy project in the residence with the installation of a 150 kW PV system on the roof of the sports centre.

Figure 8: aspect of the future sport centre building with the PV facility on the ground

Figure 9: side view drawings of the building

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036418.

- **Fuhem Foundation**

FUHEM is an independent non-profit foundation dedicated to educational activity and work on eco-social issues. FUHEM manages four different educational centres in Madrid. One of them, the Hipatia school, with more than 1,000 pupils and students, has been proposed by FUHEM to AURORA for the development of an energy community.

Figure 10: aerial view of the Hipatia school grounds

These two projects are being studied by AURORA and they are part of the social engagement strategy through the project's energy transition challenges.

3.1.8 Summary

The progress was initially stalled because the Campus-Sur REC was not created due to the lack of approval from the Rectorate of the UPM. The AURORA coordination team in Madrid has explored other strategy by the implementation of renewable energy projects in educational centres in the Community of Madrid by the Campus-Sur platform.

A first project has been selected in a primary school located one km away from UPM Campus-Sur, the so-called Colegio Centro Cultural Palomeras (CCCP). It is a private management school that uses a public building, whose owner is IVIMA, a public body of the Community of Madrid. A project consisting of 42.3 kW PV power plants and two heat pumps was successfully crowdfunded and implemented.

3.2 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal

3.2.1 Introduction

When submitting the AURORA project proposal, the AURORA team in Évora proposed the constitution of a Renewable Energy Community (REC) funded with the financial participation of academia community members only (staff and students) through a crowdfunding process. While this approach was given a positive feedback from the Administration team in place at the time, the new University Administration that was elected gave a negative opinion about this approach. They only allowed a donation scheme, which was not attractive to possible participants. This is explained in subsection 3.2.2.

Therefore, the AURORA team in Évora analysed the possibility of implementing a REC through a third-party entity. The Red Cross Delegation in Évora responded positively to implement this solution. The team in Évora approached them, considering that their core objectives and mission, seeking to have local social impact at tackling energy poverty in vulnerable families, align perfectly with the spirit of a Renewable Energy Community. During the course of AURORA, many meetings were held, technical and economic studies were developed for their facility and budgets were requested from companies. Unfortunately, the Red Cross has stopped answering and the approach stalled due to lack of their action. Despite failure, this approach has the potential to be carried out elsewhere, therefore the details are provided in subsection 3.2.3.

In parallel, the University of Évora has applied for funding for energy efficiency improvements in its buildings, in particular student residencies, which included the funds for deployment of PV facilities of approx. 750 kW. The funds were granted, and the University started the civil works in the buildings. However, due to funding delays and with public procurement issues with the civil works, the whole process started later than expected and only at the current time of this deliverable the tenders for the PV plants are being prepared. The University is registering a collective self-consumption EC that will allow the sharing of produced PV power from 6 installations (approx. 750 kW) with a total of 24 buildings distributed over the city. The whole process will only be concluded by mid-2026, which is after the end of the Aurora project. This approach is explained as a parallel attempt in subsection 3.2.4.

For now, the University of Évora, in the scope of AURORA, will follow a Virtual Energy Community approach, with its existing PV facilities. In the future, these facilities will be included in a collective self-consumption EC with the deployment of new PV installations. This mitigation approach is described in subsection 3.2.5.

3.2.2 Attempt 1 – REC within the university – failed

3.2.2.1 Conceptual design

The initial conceptual design that has been proposed and discussed with the University of Évora Administration consisted in the creation of the PV facilities in the Polo da Mitra Campus of the University of Évora, where an area of 280 hectares of land is available (Figure 11). This campus is in Valverde, in the outskirts of Évora at about 12 km from the city of Évora. Preferably, the PV Plant would be installed near the Distribution Transformer (low voltage, three-phase with 860 kVA). This internal grid has high electricity demand and had an electricity consumption of 2,478 MWh in 2023.

Figure 11: Aerial view of the location initially proposed. (Source: Google Maps)

At the beginning, the AURORA team in Évora was aiming to install a 200 kW PV system, depending on the number of participants and available funding. The PV modules were to be installed in a standard ground fixed structure with 35° of inclination and orientated to 0° South. To enhance the research nature of this system, different PV module types were being considered. The PV system was to be connected to the Distribution Transformer, enabling to achieve 100% self-consumption due to the high electricity consumption of this campus grid.

3.2.2.2 Implementation and failure

The Administration team in place at the time gave initial positive feedback. As described in D3.1 one of the threats to the proposed model was the rejection of the business model by the new University Administration, which was elected in the elections for the new Rector in April and assumed function in May 2022.

The new Administration took longer than expected to be available to discuss the AURORA REC business plan that the AURORA team in Évora had developed, after several meetings with the new administration the business plan was rejected in January 2023. The current Administration of the University of Évora indicated that the University cannot provide any benefits to the participants in the REC, even if through discounts on services and fees since it could be perceived as financial activity/operation which is out of the scope of a university.

The only solution that could be accepted by the University of Évora would be to implement the REC through a donation scheme, in which the participants make a donation to the University of Évora for the purpose of developing the energy production facilities, PV power plant, without any other retribution than the one obtained through IRS (tax returns) over the donation (25% of the donated value would be reimbursed through next year's IRS – tax returns). This approach when presented did not gather attractivity from people.

The other possibility would be creation of a private association to handle the whole process for the construction of PV plants; however, it was not considered feasible because the process would be long and very bureaucratic, including the need for people to become associates. A foundation was not possible, because the Portuguese government ordered universities to close their foundations – The university of Évora closed its foundation some years ago due to that order.

3.2.3 Attempt 2 – REC within the Red Cross – failed

3.2.3.1 Introduction

Because the initial attempt failed, efforts were made to find a suitable alternative solution with a third-party entity that could be interested in creating a REC with public participation to finance the CAPEX costs. The Red Cross delegation was the first one to be addressed considering the existing close ties and openness, and immediately demonstrated interest in analysing and discussing such solution.

3.2.3.2 Conceptual design

The Red Cross Delegation in Évora is located south to the historical city centre of Évora, with a flat rooftop without horizon constrictions that could cause significant solar radiation blockages (Figure 12 and Figure 13), however, there are limitations in available area when compared to the original solution proposed by Évora's team for the REC.

Figure 12: Évora Red Cross delegation building in Évora, aerial view. (Source: Google Maps)

Figure 13: Évora Red Cross building, street view (source: Google Maps)

Initially it was considered that the total PV power that could be installed would be roughly 45 kW, which would yield an average of 65.3 MWh/a. However, upon a thorough PV assessment study for this roof, and with the available area it was determined that the total PV power that could be installed would be 30,51 kW, which will yield an average of 41.522 MWh/a. The reduction of PV power to be installed in relation to the preliminary analysis is due to the requirement to have access corridors to the lift shaft, to HVAC machinery, and to other machinery on the rooftop. Additionally, to avoid civil construction works and renovations on the roof, a ballast structure for the PV modules was selected, obliging to the use of standard size structures to be fitted into the available.

The PV generated energy will be used for self-consumption of the building. At the ground level, there is a medical clinic dedicated to medical analysis and imaging with high energy consumption. The building electricity consumption will assure 100% self-consumption of the renewable PV energy.

The simulation details are the following:

- PV power: 30,51 kW
- Annual Yield: 1 361 kWh/kW
- Performance ratio: 81,1%
- Shading losses: 4,5%
- Estimated Annual Yield: 41.52 MWh
- Avoided CO₂ emissions: 19,903 kg/a
- REC Cross annual Energy consumption: 109.00 MWh

The simulation is being performed with the installation of PV panels tilted East and West to optimize available space usage in relation to the use of ballast structures with low tilt to increase total installed power capacity through the reduction of space in between lines to avoid shadowing.

Considering the use of standard gravity structures for the PV panels and the willingness of having 3 different PV technologies so that the PV plant can be used in the scope of citizen science the following PV technologies are being considered: Silicon type p, Silicon type n and Topcon or back contact PV modules, being the last technology yet not defined due to the need of finding and assess providers with PV modules that can fit the size of the ballast structures.

Contacts were made with EPC companies to obtain a quotation for the whole project and the total investment would be approximately 26,000.00 €.

Figure 14 shows the design of the projected PV system to be installed on the rooftop of Red Cross in Évora.

Figure 14: Projected PV system installation to be deployed onto the Red Cross rooftop for the setting up of PV facilities for the REC (source: Google Maps)

3.2.3.3 Retribution

A retribution scheme and channel was identified. A free physical card (cartão Dá) with the participant's balance (and also rechargeable by each participant) and with the possibility of using it to pay in more than 1100 stores in Portugal or Spain would be given as retribution. This possibility was approved by the Red Cross administration in May 2023.

3.2.3.4 Implementation and failure

The business plan had been approved by national Portuguese Red Cross, the crowdlending process was announced to the local community on April 18th of 2024 in a public session with the presence of Red Cross Évora Director. A presentation was given to the people present in the event, promoting AURORA project and how it would contribute towards the setting up of Red Cross Energy Community. The business plan was shown and advertised, registering demonstration of interest from the people in order to invite them to participate in the crowdlending of approx. 26,000.00 €.

Once the crowdfunding amount was achieved it was expected that the installation of the PV solar power facility runs smoothly since the Red Cross is a private entity and therefore has administrative autonomy, not being subject to public procurement law.

With the close technical support of the UEvora team, technical specifications and tender documents were produced and discussed with companies to ensure quality control procedures.

One of Red Cross's mission is to fight energy poverty and, at least, a portion of the savings obtained after distribution of remuneration through the REC members will be directed to fight energy poverty in the region through the implementation of energy saving measures for the families. The University of Évora has taken the compromise on defining specific sessions for the vulnerable families in Évora, providing first hand support with the analysis of energy bills, helping in applying for social checks for energy efficiency measures supported by environmental funds, sessions dedicated to optimizing the use of energy at home, seeking the reduction of energy costs, among other actions.

This is an important implementation to the delegation in Évora since they would be a showcase for all Red Cross delegations in Portugal.

The replication potential of this REC solution is high, amongst the Portuguese Red Cross local structures (170 local structures – Delegations and Humanitarian Centres) in all the Portuguese territory. Efforts should be directed to this action, upon practical validation and confirmation of the implemented business model by Red Cross Portugal.

Despite all the efforts, work developed, and meetings held, the Red Cross has stopped answering and the process has stalled.

3.2.3.5 Legacy and replication

After the failure of the Red Cross attempt, contacts were made with other local institutions that could be interested in implementing such approach to create a REC, as is the case of Fundação Eugénio de Almeida in Évora. Unfortunately, no advances were achieved.

Nevertheless, further contact attempts are being made in the scope of other projects, in which the team in Évora takes part. Such is the case of the municipalities of Beira Litoral (north of Alentejo Region), where the team has provided services towards a just energy transition in the region with special emphasis in the development of civic energy roadmaps for municipalities and identification of possibilities of establishing Collective Self consumption Energy Communities and Renewable Energy Communities through third party, with social care institutions. In the context of this project, the plans for two municipal collective self-consumption energy communities were proposed to two municipalities – Proença-a-Nova and Vila Velha de Ródão. The objective of such studies was to assess the technical and financial viability of those schemes so that the municipalities could apply for funding to support the development

of the PV facilities. Feasibility studies were delivered, highlighting savings and other financial benefits for the municipalities.

Although not successfully realized in the scope of Aurora project, this approach has significant replication potential, which is further discussed in section 6.3.3 of this document.

3.2.4 Parallel attempt – UE Sharing Collective Self-Consumption

3.2.4.1 Introduction

In parallel, the AURORA team in Évora had been working on the establishment of a Renewable Energy Community (REC) to facilitate collective self-consumption across the university's buildings within the city of Évora. As a UNESCO World Heritage Site, Évora is subject to strict regulations that limit visible modifications to buildings due to heritage preservation, making on-site solar energy generation within the historic centre highly challenging. Considering these restrictions, the team developed a distributed energy model, where solar energy is generated in PV installations located outside the city walls and consumed within, ensuring compliance with heritage preservation requirements, while advancing the energy transition in an area that otherwise would be left behind.

3.2.4.2 Conceptual design

For this purpose, the team supported the University in applying for funding that would allow the financing of additional PV power, up to 750 kW were considered as possible.

Portuguese legislation only permits energy sharing through the grid when a REC/Collective Self-Consumption is formally registered. Recognizing this as a viable path, the University of Évora is in the process of registering a Collective Self-Consumption, enabling solar energy produced in less restricted areas to power university facilities within the historic centre. This solution ensures that heritage conservation does not hinder access to clean energy, allowing the university to optimize self-consumption while adhering to regulatory constraints.

Figure 15: Distribution of buildings to be incorporated in the Collective Self Consumption (green marks) in City of Évora, UNESCO Heritage site area delimited in yellow.

This collective self-consumption is a pioneering initiative that merges the city's historical heritage with technological innovation. Évora is located in a UNESCO World Heritage region, the university is leading the way in energy transition

by creating a sustainable community that integrates renewable energy sources, such as solar power, to reduce carbon footprints and promote energy self-sufficiency. The Renewable Energy Community of Évora will consist of 24 key points, distributed according to the Figure 15 above, ensuring a comprehensive approach to sustainability and community involvement. This project not only focuses on clean energy production but also engages the academic and local communities, fostering awareness and active participation in building a greener and more resilient future.

3.2.4.3 Status

At the time of writing this deliverable, the technical specifications for the tenders are being drafted, and final configurations were not yet achieved. Considering that Évora, under ideal PV design installation has a specific annual PV energy production of 1606 kWh/kW, 750 kW would generate about 1.20 TWh yearly. However, the installations will not have the optimal tilt and azimuth angles due to the incorporation in buildings.

Unfortunately, the UE Sharing project will not be finished before July 2026 when the AURORA project already ends.

3.2.5 Virtual approach with existing power plant – mitigation measure

To mitigate the situation and still fulfil Aurora objectives, UÉvora is adopting a Virtual Power Plant conceptual design in the scope of AURORA. UÉvora has installed in the past several PV installations in its facilities in the city of Évora, outside the Heritage protected area. The installations have a total power of approximately 70 kW, with 60 kW in Colégio dos Leões (Figure 16) and 9.35 kW in the University's gymnasium (Figure 17). These PV installations were developed for Individual Self Consumption to reduce grid electricity demand.

Figure 16: PV installation at Colégio dos Leões

Figure 17: PV installation at the University of Évora Gymnasium

Figure 18: Aerial view Évora highlighting both PV installations

For the time being the University of Évora will operate in Virtual Energy Community scheme, with its own existing PV plants, with a power of approx. 70 kW, whilst it installs the new PV power plants with a peak power of approximately up to 750 kW and registers the collective self-consumption energy community. The timeframe for the whole process to be completed is until July 2026, which is the maximum allowed deadline for the execution of the financing.

3.2.6 Local dissemination and communication

UÉvora only set up official events dedicated to the set up the Red Cross Renewable Energy Community once it was finally confirmed that it could move on. Before, at the early stages of the project, there were several events in the framework of other work packages in which the establishment of a REC was mentioned and discussed but not on dedicated events.

On the 18th of April 2024, a first announcement of the Red Cross Évora Renewable Energy Community, in the scope of AURORA was hosted at the University of Évora premises.

During this event, a brief scope on AURORA objectives was given, the AURORA ENERGY TRACKER was presented as a tool to help the citizen realize their true environmental impact through their energy behaviours and how could they reduce their impact. The main section of this session was dedicated to the Renewable Energy Community with Red Cross, highlighting its financial model and the social impact that is expected to create for socially vulnerable families with measures and action in the energy field. The Director of Red Cross Évora was present at the event, together with the AURORA Researchers in Évora.

Figure 19: Invitation to the announcement event of the Red Cross Évora Renewable Energy Community

A second event took place at the University of Évora on the 16th of May 2024. During this event, a brief scope on AURORA objectives was given, the Aurora Energy Tracker app was presented as a tool to help the citizen realize their true environmental impact through their energy behaviours and how could they reduce their impact. The main section of this session was dedicated to the Renewable Energy Community with Red Cross, highlighting its financial model and the social impact that is expected to create for socially vulnerable families with measures and action in the energy field.

The team was asked to host the event in a hybrid format for those who could not attend the event, thus the event was hosted in a hybrid format.

Figure 20: Invitation to the event about the first renewable energy community in Évora

Despite all confirmations given by Red Cross – attending the event to announce the crowdfunding event, this approach stalled and has not moved forward. In order to describe the effort put into this project, the information is provided here nevertheless.

Regarding the University of Évora Collective Self-Consumption, it has been part of many AURORA events organized in Évora to showcase the pioneering possibility that it opens.

3.2.7 Operation after the end of the project

The University of Évora Collective self-consumption will operate beyond AURORA, providing benefits to the University of Évora and decarbonizing the historical city centre with energy produced outside of the city walls. Additionally, the team is making efforts to start registering a second collective self-consumption energy community in its campus in the outskirts of Évora, in which the research group has several PV facilities (100kW E-W tracking, 6 white BIPV modules, 3.3 kW amorphous old PV plant, is developing a 65 kW AgriPV system and throughout next year a new AgriPV plant of circa 200 kW will be developed) together with existing PV plants from the university with 32 kW.

3.2.8 Summary

The rejection of the initial business plan by the University of Évora Administration created a setback on the developing of the energy facilities. The announcement of a donation scheme, without further retribution, has not generated interest that could gather substantial capital to create even a low scale PV facility. Then, the team addressed Red Cross delegation in Évora, with whom has held many meetings and developed a lot of work for the creation of an Energy Community with Red Cross, focusing in tackling local Energy Poverty. Unfortunately, for unknown reasons Red Cross has stopped answering, despite all the interest shown, and the project stalled.

As a mitigation measure UEvora is now following a virtual approach using existing PV power plant.

In parallel, the team had been supporting the University to apply for funds to improve energy efficiency through the development of an innovative collective self-consumption energy community UEsharing, which will, once complete, be merged with the current virtual approach.

3.3 Demonstrator Site – Ljubljana, Slovenia

3.3.1 Introduction

In the beginning of the AURORA project, we started screening both the social readiness as well as the legal limitations. Obstacles were encountered in both fields. Discussions with students and poll results showed that students are not keen on financial investment, but their interest is rather on gathering knowledge about renewable energies. However, faculty and university employees possess greater financial resources. Nevertheless, if students were to contribute only symbolically, it would disproportionately increase management costs and create a financially imbalanced community, potentially discouraging employee participation. Additionally, such symbolic contributions would result in minimal financial gains, which may also discourage students.

We also investigated different legal possibilities of establishing an energy community. During a meeting between AURORA project managers, the Faculty of Electrical Engineering management, and a lawyer specializing in corporate law and renewable energy, it was discovered that Article 10 of the Higher Education Act, which addresses the legal capacity of the university and its members, is currently deemed unconstitutional. This article is presently the subject of a legal dispute and prohibits the formation of new legal entities by its members. Furthermore, as public institutions, the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and the University of Ljubljana require an explicit approval from the Government of Slovenia to establish or co-establish any new legal entity. Consequently, neither the Faculty of Electrical Engineering nor the University of Ljubljana can currently establish new legal entities

To address and circumvent these obstacles, we have decided to create a virtual energy community specifically for students, called the Student Energy Club (ŠEK). This will allow us to address the legal and social challenges while promoting energy awareness and encouraging investment in photovoltaic power plants for achieving energy independence. The purpose of this community is not primarily to raise funds for investments but rather to raise awareness about renewable energy sources among students and faculty members.

At the same time, to fulfil the AURORA objective to set up a PV power plant and to have a power plant for demonstration purposes for students and employees and to get real life data of electricity production to virtually offset individual's carbon footprint in the AURORA app, we started the procedure to install the first stage of the Solar PV Power Plant using internal funding of Faculty of Electrical Engineering. The PV power plant will offset important amount of faculty's electricity consumption and offset its CO₂ footprint as well as reduce the virtual citizen CO₂ footprint for all participants in ŠEK. This has been described in detail in D3.1.

3.3.2 Conceptual design

3.3.2.1 Faculty's PV potential

We have relied on a study of all available faculty's surfaces that can eventually be covered by PV panels. In the study, we included all the roofs, south facing facades and canopies over parking places. The study included detailed shading analysis for all surfaces and was based on a 380 W PV module with dimensions of 1755 · 1004 mm². The study on the other hand did not go in detail from civil engineering point of view and did not include static and fire safety assessments. In total, it is possible to install 432 kW of PV panels that would produce 392 MWh of electricity annually. The summarized results of the study are presented in Table 2.

PV PP Location	power (kW)	annual yield (MWh)	specific yield (kWh/kW)
Roof A - northwest	27.36	29.96	1095
Roof B - east	7.60	8.16	1074
Roof B - access house	3.80	4.32	1137
Roof B - middle	20.52	22.07	1076
Roof B - west	6.84	7.37	1078
Roof C - east	19.00	15.67	825
Roof C - west	19.00	18.39	968
Roof D - east	26.60	27.51	1034
Roof D - west	16.72	14.38	860
Roof D - south	43.23	36.61	847
Canopies - large parking	77.52	79.25	1022
Canopy - small parking	47.88	38.52	805
Facade of building A	63.46	51.58	813
Facade of building A - windows	6.00	4.10	683
Facade of building B	41.04	30.85	752
Facade of building B - extension	11.40	8.46	742
Total	437.97	397.20	907

Table 2: Estimated PV power plant capacity

3.3.2.2 AURORA PV power plant plan

For the purpose of the AURORA energy community, the PV power plant will be primarily installed on the rooftops of the buildings of Faculty of Electrical Engineering within University of Ljubljana, at the address: Trzaska cesta 25, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia. The coordinates are:

Latitude: 46.04° N

Longitude: 14.49° E

We focused on the surfaces where PV installation is the most feasible. For the canopies above parking places, a building permit would be required. As such an endeavour requires detailed elaboration and a lengthy legal procedure

(up to 2 years) that would be certainly out of AURORA’s time scope. There are even more strict requirements for the facades, where the vertical fire safety and a danger of snow falling of the modules must be considered.

Considering this, we focused on the roofs, where a PV plant is legally considered as a building appliance and does not require a building permit. However, static and fire safety assessment must still be made. The conceptual design of the power plant to be built in the scope of AURORA energy community is presented in Figure 21. The total predicted power is 190 kW, which is in the range of the AURORA project objectives for each demonstration site.

Figure 21: Conceptual design of the pilot site in Ljubljana (background source: Google Maps)

The power plant was designed in 3 stages in Table 3:

	Power	Annual Yield
Stage 1	39 kW	35 MWh
Stage 2a	87 kW	79 MWh
Stage 2b	27 kW	30 MWh
Stage 3	38 kW	35 MWh
Total:	191 kW	179 MWh

Table 3: Stages of Ljubljana demonstrator

As depicted in Figure 21 each stage is predicted to have its own connection to the faculty’s electricity grid. Due to existing infrastructure, such an approach is more cost effective than laying new cables towards a unified connection point. It is important, that all the stages are connected to the internal grid, as this allows direct self-consumption of the produced electricity. This connection scheme is labelled as PS.2 in current legislation.

3.3.2.3 Stages

3.3.2.3.1 Stage 1

In stage 1 the PVPP was anticipated to be installed onto the roof of the building B. This roof has several different orientations: flat, 7° towards south-southeast, and 7° towards north-northwest (labelled in Figure 21). Due to low roof angles, and to better align with the overall daily electricity demand (see Figure 23) we predicted installation in 10° east-west orientation. This increases the number of module orientations to seven. In addition, some modules in the west section of Stage 1 may experience some shading. To fully exploit the potential of all installed modules, we predicted the use of power optimizers. We also predicted to use modules of different technologies in the middle section of Stage 1. This section has four equally oriented parts, which will be used to install the modules with the cells of the following technologies:

- Passivated Emitter Rear Contact (PERC)
- Interdigitated Back Contact (IBC)
- Silicon HeteroJunction (SHJ)
- Tunnel Oxide Passivated Contact (TOPCon)

Special attention will be paid to find the most similar modules, i.e. to have the same laminate structure (e.g. glass-glass or glass-backsheet), the same colour of backsheet and frame, and similar cell size. This will emphasize the difference between cells of different technologies, rather than differences in module's bill of material (BOM).

We have communicated the detailed conceptual plan with QPV to prepare for monitoring and inclusion of the Ljubljana Demonstrator to the AURORA monitoring platform.

3.3.2.3.2 Stage 2

In Stage 2a the three roofs of the building D, and in Stage 2b the remaining roof of the building A are to be used for installation. The south (the lowest) roof of building D is oriented 25° towards S-SE with inclination of 5°. PVPP will be laid parallel to the roof and fastened onto the standing seam of the copper cladding. The north two roofs are horizontal, covered with bitumen layer. Since the structure of the roof is a strong concrete slab, PV modules will be installed in E-W orientation on 15° inclined triangles loaded with ballast. The remaining free roof of the building A is similar to roof B with the exception that the structure of the roof is made of wood. Here the modules are again planned to be installed in 15° E-W orientation on triangles anchored into the roof structure.

3.3.2.3.3 Stage 3

In stage 3 the final roof of building C will be covered with PV panels. This roof has two sides with 14° inclination, one facing e-NE (-115° from S) and the other facing W-SE (+65° from S). Due to sufficient inclination, the PV modules will be installed parallel to the roof and since the roof is covered with copper cladding, standing seam clamps will be used.

3.3.2.4 Production and self-consumption

As already elaborated in Deliverable 3.1, electricity demand of the faculty is usually low during weekends and holidays and over the nights because most people are at home. During working daytime hours there is an increased need for university-related operations. Daily energy consumption in 2021 of the faculty is shown in Figure 22. The base consumption of 4 MWh per day is present throughout the year, with variable increases of 1.5 to 3 MWh, depending on the circumstances. 7 days periodicity is due to the working week, and the increase in June and the first half of July is due to air conditioning. The decrease in the second half of July and August is due to the summer holidays, and the increase from October until the last week of December is due to intense study semesters and shorter days. In total in 2021 1.9 GWh was consumed, out of which about 10% can be offset by a planned 200 kW PVPP

Figure 22: Daily electricity consumption of Faculty of Electrical Engineering at University of Ljubljana during 2021.

A typical working hour increase corresponds very well to the predicted generation of the power plant with modules installed in a 10° east-west orientation. Detailed circumstances around May 1 are shown in Figure 23. The chart shows that with a proposed 200 kW solar system, all the generated electricity will be used on site. In the case of an unlikely surplus, electricity will be exported to the grid and will be sold to the electricity provider at an annual power purchase agreement negotiated by market price.

Figure 23: Electricity consumption of Faculty of Electrical Engineering at University of Ljubljana and electricity production of a proposed 200 kW PVPP.

3.3.3 Implementation 1 – Staged attempt – failed

3.3.3.1 Introduction

As described in D3.1 and the Conceptual design chapter above, our initial plan was to build the AURORA demonstrator in stages. This section describes our first attempt to realise Stage 1. Unfortunately, this attempt failed because the selected installer lost interest with our installation due to many problems that arose during the implementation. Despite failure, we nevertheless keep this chapter in the deliverable, not only to demonstrate the effort, but more importantly to provide the insight to the process to the public.

3.3.3.2 Grid connection permit

The first step towards realization of the first stage was to apply for a permit for grid connection from the grid operator. As this may be a lengthy process that does not require much effort, we elaborated the application and submitted it to the grid operator after approval, even before the start of the AURORA project. The permission was granted in a few months' time and is valid for two years.

3.3.3.3 Quotations

In the second step we contacted several installers to provide the offers for the first stage. After we received the quotations of the first round, we selected three installers with the lowest prices and quality quotes and invited them to pay a site visit and provide quotations that are more detailed. Due to increased demand for PV power plants in the self-consumption scheme, installers were busy and finally we have only had a site visit by two installers, who provided a realistic quotation that included everything that was foreseen in our conceptual design and that considered all the requirements from the grid operator.

3.3.3.4 Legal requirements

After internally accepting the quotation, we proceeded with three steps in parallel:

- preparation of the contract
- fire safety assessment
- static assessment

3.3.3.4.1 Contract

Preparation of the contract was taken over by our administration, while the selected installer provided two subcontractors for fire safety and static assessment.

3.3.3.4.2 Fire safety assessment

Fire safety assessment passed with the only remark about the roof of the house where the stairs come to the roof. Since this is an emergency exit, the roof must fulfil the REI 60 requirement, meaning that in case of fire on the roof (i.e. the panels or the wiring on the roof) the roof remains structurally solid for 60 minutes despite the ongoing fire. Since the data of the structure of this roof was not available and the estimation was that this roof does not meet the REI 60 requirement, we had two options:

- a) not to install the 10 predicted modules and reduce the installed power for about 4 kW
- b) rebuild the roof to meet the REI 60 requirement and proceed the installation

Since the actual structure of the roof could not be identified and since the loss of power was only 4 kW, we decided for option a.

3.3.3.4.3 Static assessment

The first static assessment revealed that the roof not strong enough to bear additional load of PV modules. First the roof alone, made of corrugated sheet metal with Styrofoam inserts and bitumen layer on top, cannot support direct mounting of the sub frame for the modules. Therefore, anchoring the module subframe directly into steel structure is required. Second, the steel structure of the fifth floor and the roof is also not strong enough. The reason for failed static assessment is that the faculty-building original only had four floors. The fifth floor was added later and in order not to overload the existing structure of the building, it was built very lightweight using metal framing. Metal is very refined building material with well-defined structural properties; therefore, the design of the framing only considers small safety factors. In order to keep the structure light, the frame was designed and built to support the load and all the safety factors known at that time.

The static assessment predicted two reinforcement measures for the steel structure:

- a) Reinforcement of the main horizontal beam (I 260, green in Figure 24) that supports the roof substructure with additional diagonal metal arms (HOP □ 120x60x4, cyan in Figure 24).

- b) Reinforcement of the top rectangular pipe (HOP \square 90x90x4, yellow in Figure 25) that carries the roof with two vertical pillars (HOP \square 30x30x2.5, blue in Figure 25) that are supported by a pre-tensioned steel wire (D=1.6, cyan in Figure 25).

Figure 24: Structural reinforcements of the roof at UL: Reinforcement of the main horizontal beam I 260.

Figure 25: Structural reinforcements of the roof at UL: Reinforcement of the top rectangular pipe (HOP \square 90x90x4)

3.3.3.5 Structural reinforcements of the roof

Based on the requirement that the module subframe must be anchored directly into the steel structure of the roof, the subframe was redesigned. Although we are not experts in civil engineering, we (the UL AURORA team) also revised the calculation and noted that the modules do not cover the complete roof area. This resulted in a new estimation of additional roof load, which did not require reinforcement of the main horizontal beam (point a above). However, reinforcement of the top rectangular pipe (point b above) was still required.

Accordingly, we asked the selected installer to find a subcontractor, who would come to a site visit and prepare a quotation for this reinforcement. In the after covid period every company in the building sector in Slovenia is overbooked and it was difficult to find potential contractors that would be willing to do this. To make this work even less attractive, there is only about 1 m of free height below the roof in the very dusty and hot attic. A subcontractor came for a site visit but did not provide a quotation in about a month. Another subcontractor provided by the installer also visited the site and discovered that the actual steel structure of the roof deviates slightly from the blueprints in a positive way:

- a) the top rectangular pipe HOP \square 90x90x4 (yellow in Figure 25) is actually a stronger rectangular pipe HOP \square 100x100x4, and
- b) There are five instead of four parallel top rectangular pipes HOP \square 100x100x4 (yellow and black, respectively, in Figure 26) on the north flank of the roof, which reduce the span between them and the effective area which determines the load that each pipe has to carry from 250 to 200 cm. Still, the span on the south flank remains at 240 cm.

Figure 26: Steel frame of the roof at UL. Designed state in black, actual state in yellow.

We communicated these observations to the civil engineer that produced the first static assessment, but despite this his final assessment still required reinforcements.

3.3.3.6 Revised static assessment

Due to delays, we also started searching for a subcontractor on our own. We found a contractor that first visited a site and then checked the first static assessment. Several mistakes were found in the first static assessment:

- the main criterion to fail the assessment was too high deflection of the rectangular pipe due to chosen criterion of $L/300$,
- the rectangular pipe was not considered continuous but discontinuous,
- two other mistakes not related to failure of this part of static assessment.

In response to point *a* above, there are three criteria for stability of horizontal members:

- Tension check: calculated in the first static assessment to 85% of capacity → passed
- Stability check: calculated in the first static assessment to 78% of capacity → passed
- Deflection criterion is set based on the load and aesthetic function of the elements above the horizontal member. Since there is only a roof without any walls above the horizontal member, this criterion may be reduced to $L/200$ which → met

The point *b* above (i.e. rectangular pipes are continuous instead of discontinuous) further reduces material utilization and deflection. Thus, we finally proved that the roof's steel structure is strong enough and that reinforcement is not required.

3.3.3.7 Revised quotation

Still, the roof alone was not strong enough for direct installation of the modules, therefore proper design and anchoring the subframe of the modules to the steel substructure is still required. The installer with its subcontractor then designed the subframe for the modules and predicted delicate anchoring paying attention to water tightness of the bitumen roof.

They produced a quotation with a price of just under 2 €/W, which is almost double of the initial price. In other words, the module sub framing with the anchoring represents over 50% of the PV power plant costs, compared to usual 10 to 20%. Such a price is not economically justified nor is it a good example for a demonstrator; therefore, we are revising the proposed anchoring detail, which is explained in section 3.3.4

3.3.3.8 Additional efforts

3.3.3.8.1 Selection of modules of different technologies

According to description in section 3.3.2.3 a variety of four different module types was planned to be installed in the central section of Stage 1. As most of the installers (at least in Slovenia) only supply several modules for which they have well established supply chains, none of the installers was willing to provide modules out of their usual assortment.

Therefore, we made a market screening of suppliers that sell a variety of modules and ship them to Slovenia. As we wanted all the modules to have as similar properties as possible except for the cell types and due to PV module shortage, this turned up to be quite a difficult task. We have secured the quotations for all four anticipated module types already at the receipt of the first more detailed quotations. We had to use different suppliers to obtain the similar frame-backsheet-glass combination for all four module types.

We have made a list of selected modules already three times, as the list is only valid as long as the supplier has the modules in stock or in arrival.

3.3.3.8.2 Roof renovation by sandwich metal roof

In parallel to all the developments above we also searched for other solutions. Because the topmost layer of the roof needs to be renovated, we also acquired a quote for a complete change of bitumen roof for a corrugated metal roof that would enable installation of the power plant directly on the roof. Unfortunately, that option was about 3 times more expensive than a simple additional layer of bitumen overlay.

3.3.3.8.3 Test site relocation to gain additional space

During the lengthy procedure, we also continued with a project to move the test site from the northwest side of the Stage 1 roof to a new test site on the other faculty's building. At the time of the first attempt, the new test site was being built, and the old test site was to be transferred to that location freeing up space for additional 24 modules at the Stage 1 of the power plant.

3.3.3.9 Termination

During this implementation attempt many barriers arose due to the complicated roof situation. The static assessment of the roof was done twice by the contractor's subcontractor including some revisions that still did not lead to successful evaluation. We needed to find another civil engineer that properly evaluated the roof and made installation possible. Fire safety assessment did not allow modules to be installed on the small roof. The planning for module substructure had to be evaluated twice to conform with the static assessments. The selected contractor visited the site several times and provided four different quotations. In the later stages of the project the communication with the contractor was becoming increasingly more seldom and difficult. Finally, the contractor provided the last quotation, which was too expensive, firstly for the PVPP to be economically viable, and secondly it was above the price limit after which a public tender is required by the law. Due to the combination of all these factors and due to the timeframe of AURORA project, we decided to abandon this approach and proceed with the holistic approach based on public tender.

3.3.4 Implementation 2 – holistic approach based on public tender

3.3.4.1 Introduction

As described in section 3.3.3.9, we were forced to abandon the staged approach and proceed with the holistic approach, where power plants on all four roofs would be installed together. As the project was now significantly larger, also the price was significantly higher which required a different legal path using a public tender. Therefore, we prepared the documentation for the public tender – described in detail in 3.3.4.3. As we have learnt from the first implementation approach that the statics can be problematic, we also immediately hired a civil engineer to provide a static assessment for all four buildings.

3.3.4.2 Static assessment

Since the static assessment was very problematic in the first approach, we started with the static assessment of all the buildings already before terminating the first implementation approach.

The buildings of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering have been built at separate times. While some parts (basis of building C) are older than 70 years, the newest parts (west part of building B) are about 35 years old. Some buildings (building A and east part of building B) had another lightweight floor added on top. In addition, the roofs of the buildings are not the same and were changed several times. Unfortunately, the collection of blueprints and all static assessments is not very well maintained and not digitalized. Therefore, the search for the correct documentation and tracking of the interventions is difficult and time consuming and often requires in the field checks of constructions, and, in the worst-case, search of documentation at third parties. Consequently, the whole static assessment lasted from M20 (July 2023) to M29 (April 2024), while providing intermediate results by M26 (Jan 2024) to be included in the public tender documentation.

Due to the lack of the exact documentation, several structures had to be modelled again:

- Fourth floor of Building A with wooden roof substructure
- Part of fourth floor and wooden roof substructure above the elevator machine room in Building A
- Fifth floor of Building B with steel roof substructure
- Complete wooden roof structure of building C

Modelling examples are shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Examples of roof structure models for static assessment of the buildings.

Finally, the results of the static assessment were positive and allow installation of PVPPs on all roofs:

- Roof A: above roof with anchoring into wooden substructure
- Roof B, east: above roof with anchoring into steel substructure
- Roof B, west: on roof, use of ballast allowed after pebbles removal
- Roof C: on roof, using standing seam as an anchor
- Roof D (upper two roofs): on roof, use of ballast allowed

3.3.4.3 Public tender

In the holistic approach installing four PVPPs on all available roofs sums up to about 200 kW, which in rough estimate is about 200 k€. The realization of project of this size requires in a public institution in Slovenia requires a public tender. To do so, we revised the Conceptual design (3.3.2) to comply with the issues learnt during the failed staged implementation. This resulted in a design very similar to the old one. The new design is shown in Figure 21

Figure 28: Design of the pilot site in Ljubljana used in the tender (background source: Google Maps)

The technical specification in the tender was written in such a way that it did not prefer a certain installer. The modules were not selected, nor was the sub construction (apart from static requirements) or the inverters.

The specific requirements were:

- Modules with efficiency above 20%
- Different inverters on different roofs
- Complete service from planning, via obtaining grid permit, to final installation and connection to the grid
- Compliance with static report

Site visit prior to public tender application was not required (because such requirement is not allowed by the law, but it was available for every applicant and very much encouraged).

The selection criterion was based on:

- Specific price of the power plan (€/W) (main criterion)
- Module efficiency (additional points)
- Module efficiency after 25 years (additional points)

The legal part of the public tender documentation was prepared by our administration as it requires law knowledge and experience. The public tender was published online at https://www.enarocanje.si/Obrazci/?id_obrazec=505544 in M26 (Jan 2024)

The timeline of the tender was as follows:

Date	Status	Days	Next Action	Risk
17.01.2024	Tender open	20	Collecting quotes	
5.02.2024	Tender closed	7	Evaluation of applications	No suitable application
12.02.2024	Tender decision	7	Waiting for legal capacity	Complaints
19.02.2024	Legal capacity	7	Contract signing	

Table 4: UL Tender Timeline

Interest for the tender was greater than anticipated:

- 7 companies visited our premises
- 4 companies did not apply
- 4 applications were received (3 with visit, 1 without visit)
- 2 applications were eliminated due to non-compliance with technical requirements

Out of the two remaining companies, Enertec d.o.o. was selected as a contractor due to the lower specific price as well as for the highest efficiency and most reliable modules. The contract was signed by both parties on March 8 2024.

3.3.4.4 Revised design

The conceptual design was not a strict requirement for the tender, and companies could change their designs slightly to match their module size, sub construction limitations and/or provide a more optimized solution. The contractor will use the PhonoSolar PS440M8GFH-18/VNH modules. These are glass-glass modules with TOP-Con cells and measure 1722 x 1134 mm². A revised design was proposed and reviewed. The final iteration is presented in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Revised design of the pilot site in Ljubljana as developed by contractor Enertec and University of Ljubljana (background source: Google Maps)

There are several changes compared to the conceptual design (3.2.2):

- Roof A: changed configuration from triangular E-W to parallel with the roof, modified layout to fit the modules
- Roof A: added modules on the roof of the elevator machine room (+32 PVMs)
- Roof B east: removed the modules due to fire safety and insufficient gaps (-30 PVMs)
- Roof B middle: changed configuration from triangular E-W to parallel with the roof. Modified the layout accordingly and increased number of types of research modules to 6 (+6 PVMs)
- Roof B west: added another row of modules (+6 PVMs)
- Roof C: modified layout (+28 PVMs)
- Roof D south: removed from planning due to shading and insufficient documentation (-114 PVMs)
- Roof D north: modified layout, removed gaps (+18 PVMs)

Summing up all the changes and considering higher module power of 440 W (Research modules have slightly lower power as listed in Table 6), total newly installed capacity increased to 206 kW as shown in Table 5.

Roof	modules	power [kW]	details
Roof A	104	45,8	
North - main	72	31,7	string & optimizers (12)
South - elevator room	32	14,1	string
Roof B	108	45,6	
West	48	21,1	individual optimizers
East - research	60	24,5	individual optimizers
Roof C	128	56,3	
East	64	28,2	string & optimizers
West	64	28,2	string & optimizers
Roof D	132	58,1	
East	78	34,3	string
West	54	23,8	microinverters
Total	472	205,8	

Table 5: Summary of demonstrator installation at University of Ljubljana

The aim of research modules is to evaluate different cell technologies, namely PERC, TOP Con, SHJ and IBC. This requires careful selection of the modules, so that other influential factors are minimized. Care has been taken to find the modules with the same configuration (Glass, black back sheet, black frame). Adding to that are two additional TOP Con and SHJ modules, both with glass, glass, black frame configuration, where the TOP Con modules will be the same as the majority. A list of research modules is presented in Table 6.

#	Type	Manufacturer	Model	cover	enc.	frame	Power	Efficiency
1	TOP Con	Phono Solar	PS440M8GFH-18/VNH	g/g	trp	bk	440 W	22,5%
2	TOP Con	FuturaSun	FU420M Silk Nova All Black	g/bs	bk	bk	420 W	21,5%
3	PERC	Solar Fabrik	Mono 405 W S4 Halfcut	g/bs	bk	bk	405 W	20,7%
4	SHJ	MeyerBruger	Black 390 W	g/bs	bk	bk	390 W	21,2%
5	SHJ	MeyerBruger	Bifacial 380 W	g/g	trp	bk	380 W	20,7%
6	ZIBC	FuturaSun	FU420M Zebra Pro AllBlack	g/bs	bk	bk	420 W	21,3%

Table 6: List of research modules with their basic properties.

Legend: *g* – glass, *bs* – backsheet, *trp* – transparent, *bk* - black

In addition to different module types, we also requested that different inverters, optimizers and their combinations are used:

- Roof A: String inverter with optimizers behind the elevator machine room
- Roof B: Solar Edge with single module optimizers for accurate per module energy measurement
- Roof C: String inverter with optimizers to avoid and evaluate shading effect of higher buildings in the south
- Roof D East: String optimizer
- Roof D West: Microinverters

3.3.4.5 Execution

Collaboration with the contractor was cooperative and productive. After signature of the contract on March 8 2024 contractor visited our premises to check the roofs again for details to provide accurate revised design. Based on their visit they proposed a revised design, which was slightly altered and confirmed by us (described in detail above in 3.3.4.4) They also gathered and prepared required documentation to prepare grid permit applications. They filed in the applications on April 9. While waiting for the grid permit, the contractor prepared the detailed design plans. The grid connection permits were issued on May 22, and final design plans were finished on June 17. According to the contract, the contractor had 45 days to finish the installation, however our maintenance requested roof renovation prior to installation, which was significantly delayed due to unavailability of the roof contractor. Therefore, an annex was signed, which transferred the 45 days limit after the roof renovation was complete.

Despite the annex, the contractor immediately began work on the roofs C and D where roof renovation was not required. The modules on roofs C and D were installed in July.

In parallel work also started on

- fire safety assessment,
- internal grid connection adaptation and
- relocation of small old PV power plant on roof D.

Fire safety assessment required one window change and one window blockage to ensure EI60 fire rating of respective walls. This required searching for two more contractors to do this work. **Internal grid connection** adaptation further required approved design plan and proof that internal installation is appropriate for connection of the power plants. The documentation was made by an electrical engineer that made the detailed design plans for the powerplants, as he was already familiar with the project and the buildings. During the design, additional safety feature with centralised remote emergency shutoff switches was predicted. **Relocation of small old PV power plant** was done by members of our laboratory. All these works required significant additional effort from the UL Aurora team to organize everything. These works including roof renovation caused additional delay of the project but were finished until December 2024, except for finalization of the internal grid adaptation.

The installer continued with the installation of the PV modules first on roof A, followed by roof B, which were both completed in December 2024. At that time the contractor started preparing grid connection application, which required four additional documents:

- a statement that the PV power plant is in line with building regulations,
- a cultural conservation consent since the faculty is located within an archaeological site,
- a water consent since the faculty is located within a water protected area and
- a power purchase agreement (PPA)

To save time, the contractor submitted incomplete applications, while we were acquiring the required documents. The first three documents were acquired already in December, which allowed to contractor to complete the submitted applications. The PPA was in the beginning of January. The adaptation of internal grid and AC wiring of all the electrical cabinets were also complete in January and pre-approved by the grid operator.

The grid connection was finally done on February 25. The power plants are operational since that. The aerial photography of the powerplants is shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: PV Power Plants installed on the roofs of the Faculty on Electrical Engineering of University of Ljubljana
There were some technical challenges and deficiencies, which were identified already by the contractor, or by the Aurora UL team performing quality control checks. Among them were:

- Inverter on roof C failed to start despite being wired according to detailed design plan which complied with the specifications and installation manual of the inverter. It turned out that connected strings of optimizers were too short, despite being long enough according to inverter specification Series connection of pairs of strings was permissible and solved the startup issue.
- Improper wiring was discovered in the junction boxes on the AC side of microinverters. The contractor fixed the wiring immediately after being notified about the issue.
- Tigo system on roof A failed to report status and production. The culprit was erroneous connection between two communication devices of the Tigo system. The connection was repaired.
- Mixed location of several modules connected to microinverters. The modules were reconnected, and the positions were corrected in the monitoring system.

All of these were addressed and resolved in an appropriate time by the contractor.

When all the systems were online, a local demonstrator display was designed. It runs as a service on the local server that communicates with all inverters and monitoring systems via Modbus over TCP/IP, aggregates all PV power plant production data as well as electricity demand or supply from or to the grid, and finally displays this information on a publicly available website <https://se.fe.uni-lj.si>. This website is then displayed on a videowall in the hall of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering (Figure 31).

Figure 31: Local demonstrator display at University of Ljubljana

With all the works completed, and final documentation of the works carried out prepared, the handover was officially done on April 10 (Figure 32).

The timeline is summarized in Table 7:

Date	Status
8.03.2024	Contract signed
9.04.2024	Grid permit application submitted
22.5.2024	Grid permit issued
17.6.2024	Detailed design plans finalized
July 2024	Installation of PV modules on roofs C and D
Summer 2024	Fire safety assessment and adaptations Internal grid connection planning and adaptations Relocation of old PV power plant on roof D
Autumn 2024	Roof A and B renovation
Dec 2024	Installation of PV modules on roofs A and B Grid connection application submitted Acquisition of additional documentation and permits
Jan 2025	AC wiring complete and pre-approved Power purchase agreement signed
25.2.2025	Grid connection Bug fixes
10.4.2025	Handover
18.6.2025	Inauguration @ SLO-PV

Table 7: UL PVPP Implementation 2 Timeline

The formal inauguration of the power plants took place on the occasion of the 11th Slovenian Photovoltaic Conference – SLO-PV 2025. The last talk of the conference was dedicated to the whole journey of the powerplants, the Student Energy Club, and the Aurora Energy Tracker app. It was followed by the inauguration (Figure 33).

Figure 32: The handover of the powerplants between the representative of Enertec d.o.o and representative of Aurora UL team

Figure 33: Inauguration of the powerplant during 11. Slovenian Photovoltaic Conference 2025

3.3.5 Local dissemination and communication

In Ljubljana local dissemination and communication was focused on raising awareness, educating people about their energy consumption and corresponding carbon footprints. The actions listed and described here may also be listed in other work packages, as we took advantage of certain events to promote different topics of Aurora. We have put a strong emphasis on live events where we organized several events and also contributed to events organized by other entities.

In the very beginning of the project, even before the start of the T3.2 we organized two meetings with students to test their readiness for the Aurora project. Based on the responses we realized that significant effort will need to be invested in raising awareness which was of key importance for establishing the Student Energy Club as well as for the course of the project, including the initially staged attempt of the demonstrator installation.

To raise awareness, we first organized two events in May 2022. At these events we presented the complete Aurora approach to energy self-sufficiency using community power plants and promoted our demonstrator.

We also presented the whole Aurora approach in two Slovenian Photovoltaic conferences – SLO-PV, and then Student Energy Club also organized several events to attract students.

The list of events is shown in Table 8:

Event title	Date
Aurora Presentation to Students	28 January 2022
Aurora Presentation to Students	14 March 2022
Presentation of the Aurora project to students of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering in Ljubljana	24 May 2022
Young people for the energy transition - Let's go to ŠEK	27 May 2022
8th Slovenian Photovoltaic Conference SLO-PV 2022	14 June 2022
ŠEK At the Extracurricular Activities Fair of the University of Ljubljana	21 December 2022
ŠEK Invites You to Coffee and Donuts	21 December 2022
Presentation of ŠEK & AURORA to students	23 May 2023
9th Slovenian Photovoltaic Conference - SLO-PV 2023	07 June 2023
Premiere of the Aurora Mobile Application	23 November 2023
Lecture on Photovoltaics at the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics	27 May 2024
ŠEK At the Extracurricular Activities Fair of the University of Ljubljana	10 October 2024
2nd National Citizen Science Event	4 December 2024
27. Energy days – Special Recognition Award of Virtual Energy Community at University of Ljubljana as a demonstration project from public sector	14 and 15 April 2025
11th Slovenian Photovoltaic Conference – SLO-PV 2025: Presentation and Inauguration	18 June 2025

Table 8: List of dissemination and communication events in Ljubljana mainly focused on WP3 activities

We were also organizing events, where the main focus was either Citizen Researcher Meetings, app use and promotion and workshops, reported in deliverables of WP1, WP2 and WP4, respectively. Nevertheless, we also used those events to promote the Aurora Demonstrator and the Aurora Rationale.

In addition to live events, we also used websites:

- Aurora Ljubljana Demo site – <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/ul-main/>
- Student Energy Club – <http://www.s3k.si/>

And social media channels:

- All listed at linktree – <https://linktr.ee/s3k.si>

To spread the word about Aurora, as well as to post interesting news from the field of self-sufficiency and energetics.

3.3.6 Operation after the end of the project

In case of AURORA demonstrator at University of Ljubljana we were forced to split it to two parts. First is the informal social community *Student Energy Club* (SEK) and the second is the demonstrator power plant.

Although SEK was established as an idea of the Aurora project, it is now independent entity connecting students in energy related matters, on one hand performing activities envisaged by the Aurora project (raising awareness, organizing workshops and events, etc.), while on the other it is also involved in other projects not initiated by the Aurora project (Hackathon organization with EESTEC, collaboration with centre for extracurricular activities of University of Ljubljana). Therefore, the SEK will continue to exist and operate even after the end of the AURORA project.

The demonstrator power plants are funded and owned by the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and are therefore in this aspect independent of the AURORA project, which implies that the power plants will continue to operate after the end of the project. UL will also keep the monitoring displays running, as this is in line with UL goals to promote renewable energies.

3.3.7 Summary

The mission of installing a 200 kW PVPP on the roof of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering of UL was very demanding. During its course we have experienced many obstacles. We took the first step to obtain the grid connection permit for a part of the installation even before the official start of the AURORA project.

In the beginning of the project we decided for the staged approach. The grid permission was granted and we used it for the first stage. We proceeded with searching the installers and gathered quotes. At that time, we encountered the first obstacle, when the developments in forming the official energy community based on cooperative or other legal entity were not successful due to legal reasons. But we have found a mitigation strategy to continue with the power plant project funded by internal funds. Then the second obstacle arose when the negative static assessment blocked the project for several months, while we searched for alternatives. We have put great efforts to understand the problems and find solutions. We were also lucky, that the mistakes were found in the first static assessment, and that finally we were able to get a positive static assessment. When we thought that we have won the battle, the third obstacle stemmed up when the communication with installer stalled and they provided the quotation with doubled price due to complicated lightweight anchoring detail to the bitumen roof. At that point we were already behind the schedule of the Aurora project, therefore we abandoned the staged approach.

Instead, we started with the holistic approach, where all available roofs are covered by four power plants. Since the investment now increased to estimated 200 k€, we were legally required to take the public tender approach. We prepared the documentation, carried out the public procurement and selected the contractor. The contractor obtained grid permit and prepared the detailed documentation for the power plant. The PV modules on roofs C and D were installed July 2025. The rest of the summer and the beginning of autumn was spent arranging the roof renovations of roofs A and B, internal grid adaptation and relocation of old power plant on roof D. In December 2024 these works were complete and the modules were also installed on the roofs A and B. Also in December the first grid connection application was submitted and some additional permits, required for grid connection, were obtained. In January the AC wiring was complete and on February 25 2025 all the power plants were grid connected. After resolving some issues, the handover took place on April 10, and finally the inauguration was made on June 18, 2025.

The holistic approach with the public tender turned out to be a good solution in part due to the well-prepared tender documentation, which was based on the experiences learned during the failed stage approach. There were also additional complications and barriers that further delayed the execution, but with the help of the skilled and responsible installer we were able to find solutions for all of them and complete the installations.

3.4 Demonstrator Site – Aarhus, Denmark

3.4.1 Introduction

The model adopted in Aarhus follows the “prosumer via third party” framework. The energy community is set up in the form of a solar cooperative, where students and staff from Aarhus University (AU) can crowdfund by buying shares of the rooftop solar installation. The cooperative, as an independent entity from AU, owns the solar installation. This is due to the fact that the university law does not allow AU to become a share-owner of the cooperative or receive financial returns through the yearly dividends.

Since AU does not own the buildings at Nobelparken (rooftop PV system installation site), the solar cooperative rents the rooftops from the building owner FEAS Erhverv P/S through a 3-party agreement, which involves the solar cooperative, FEAS and AU. In this agreement, FEAS agrees to lease the rooftops of 3 buildings in Nobelparken to the cooperative for photovoltaic system installation, and AU agrees to allocate a technical room from their current tenancy in Nobelparken to the cooperative to house equipment such as inverters. Between the solar cooperative and AU, there is a separate agreement, detailing the delivery and purchase of electricity. Members of the energy community, or shareowners of the cooperative, receive annual economic returns depending on the percentage of shares they own and the amount of electricity that is produced and sold to AU yearly. Based on the newest Danish legislation, AU will be considered as “prosumer via third party” and save costs on transporting electricity and grid fees. There are a few conditions for this framework: (1) requirements for close and real geographical connection between production and consumption, (2) if the production facility is owned by a third party, the third party must remain subject to the consumer's instructions, and (3) the third party itself cannot self-consume the electricity. All of these conditions are met in the Aarhus demonstrator.

As this legal framework is new in Denmark, it takes longer time for the administrators in FEAS and AU to approve the proposed approach. After the initial positive feedback on the approach in November 2022, negotiations regarding the detailed terms in the agreements went on for another 6 months. In August 2023, the solar cooperative is officially founded with the name Universitetets Energisælleskab F.M.B.A (UEF). The registration of UEF to the Danish Business Authority was accepted in September 2023. By December 2023, the agreement between UEF and AU regarding the delivery and purchase of electricity, and the 3-party agreement between FEAS, AU, and UEF regarding the use of the rooftops in Nobelparken are signed by all parties.

The crowdfunding process started in Aarhus in November 2023 through a reservation process, where people could pay a small amount of money to reserve shares (to reserve 1 share, people are asked to pay 100 kr or 13.4 €). This process lasted till April 2024. During this time, the board of directors of UEF contacted local contractors and formed a technical review committee, who reviewed the offers from contractors. By May 2024, the UEF board has made decision on the contractor offer, and 900 shares are reserved. The reserved shares are paid in full by members by July 2024 (with exception of 33 shares, where people withdrew interest). The installation of the PV panels took place from June to August (extended period due to summer holiday) 2024, and they are connected to the grid in September 2024. Since then, the installation has been producing electricity to AU.

3.4.2 Conceptual design

The initial agreed site for the PV plant is on the rooftops of Buildings 1481, 1483 and 1485 at Nobelparken, at the following address: Jens Chr. Skous Vej 2, 8000 Aarhus and Jens Chr. Skous Vej 4, 8000 Aarhus. The coordinates are:

- Latitude: 56.17° N
- Longitude: 10.21° E

The complex comprises of 3 building blocks, which are connected by intermediate steps of lower heights. A Google Map image is shown in the following figure. All roofs are flat on these buildings (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Aerial view of roofs of the building used by AU (source: Google Maps)

Since the site in Aarhus includes three rooftop areas, it makes sense that the installation includes 3 PV arrays (one array on every rooftop) and 3 inverters (one inverter for each building). A Figure 35 from the preliminary simulation using PVsyst for the conceptual design is shown below. For safety reasons, the panels in the proposed design are kept 2m away from all edges of the buildings, and the skylight windows and other obstacles that are already existent on the roof are taken into consideration in the placement of PV panels. The final configuration of the installation is described in the next section.

Figure 35: Planned solar installation on the roofs in Aarhus

From initial simulation results, we conclude that the PV panels will be oriented 19° EAST (following the longest dimension) in the buildings due to the following reasons: (a) the annual energy production will only be 1% lower than

the SOUTH orientation, and (b) this will maximize the use of the rooftop space and ease the mechanical mounting. The PV panels could be mounted in landscape configuration and with a tilt angle of 20° to maximize annual electricity generation while minimizing wind loads. The final configuration of the installation is described in the next section.

For the installation, we plan to use different technologies of monocrystalline solar cells including monofacial PERC, bifacial PERC and TOPCon technologies. The plan is to have one technology per rooftop. By doing this, researchers could test and compare the performance of different solar cell technologies installed in the same environment. Due to our agreement with FEAS to minimize CO₂ emissions of the panels, it is stated in the specifications to contractors that PV modules produced by a European manufacturer will be positively evaluated.

3.4.3 Implementation and current status

3.4.3.1 Updated design

On Feb 1, 2024 we sent an invitation to 11 Danish companies to give offers to supply, install and commission UEF's rooftop PV system at Nobelparken. The technical specification in the invitation was developed based on a template developed by QPV and AURORA project partners, while accounting for the specific requirement for the installation in Aarhus. In addition to the technical specifications, 3 site visits to the rooftop and technical rooms in Nobelparken were arranged, on 9 Feb, 15 Feb and 20 March, respectively. 5 companies (1komma5 or previously known as Viasol, KlimaEnergi, CO2Pro, SolarPark, PhoenixTag) joined these site visits. The companies were given 3 weeks to prepare proposals. Eventually, we received offers from 4 companies (1komma5, KlimaEnergi, CO2Pro, and SolarPark). A review committee comprised of volunteers in the community with expertise and experience in relevant field was appointed by the board of UEF to conduct the evaluation. The review committee had 2 discussions, on 14 March and 4 April, respectively. Some companies submitted revised proposals based on the review committee's questions after the committee's first discussion on 14 March. In the end, the company 1komma5 Danmark is selected to carry out the project.

During the review and discussion with contractors, the design of the installation has gone through some updates. The final details of the design are accepted by the board of UEF, and we describe in the following section the updated design.

Instead of using 3 rooftops as originally planned, the updated design proposes using 2 rooftops (the left most 2 buildings in Figure 19). Each rooftop is expected to comprise about 50 kW solar panels and a 40 kW Huawei inverter. The solar panels will be oriented facing east-west orientation using a ballast mounting system. The review committee reckons that the electricity generation is slightly lower in east-west orientation than south orientation, but the total system weight will be lighter with lower wind load, which is a strong factor to consider in Danish weather. The east-west delta configuration requires a ballast system that weighs approximately 15 kg/m², while the south-oriented ballast system weighs approximately 25 kg/m². In addition, the proposed solution uses only 2 rooftops, thus saving cost for additional wiring and electrical connection to the building, less time needed for the crane placing the solar panels on the rooftop, and installation and risks associated with using a third rooftop. Finally, an East-West solution produces more energy during morning and evening hours when energy is more valuable and more likely to be needed in the buildings (compared to a production concentrated at midday with a south-facing system).

Additionally, based on follow-up statics analysis (detailed in next section) and site inspection, we decided that the solar PV panels will be installed on one side of the fall line on the rooftop to avoid covering the drainage holes.

An illustration of the updated design is shown in Figure 36.

Based on the agreement between FEAS and UEF, we should strive to select solar panels with higher supply chain traceability and prove that the PV system will be CO₂ neutral in 6 years' time, considering the emissions produced in the manufacturing process. As a result, we specified in the technical specifications, that panels produced in Europe (e.g. Meyer Burger) will be positively reviewed. However, the proposals we received do not include Meyer Burger

panels, probably due to the fact that their manufacturing facility in Europe is being closed down at the time of contractor offers.

For the installation, two types of solar panels from different manufacturers are proposed: Longi and Maxeon. Longi panels are monocrystalline TOPCon with back contacts, and the Maxeon panels are bifacial TOPCon. A short summary of the two panels is shown in the Table below. The final design is to use each on one rooftop and compare their performance in Danish weather. By doing this, researchers could test and compare the performance of different solar cell technologies installed in the same environment. This also aligns with AU's initiative of encouraging researchers to use the campus as a "living lab".

Panels	Longi panels	Maxeon panels
PV modules	half-cut solar cells, monofacial TOPCon, single glass, 21% efficiency, maximum degradation 0.55%	TOPCon bifacial solar cells, glass-glass, up to 22.5% efficiency, maximum degradation 0.4%
Mounting	east-west orientation with "delta" ballast mounting and 10° inclination (approximately 15 kg/m ²)	
Inverter	Huawei SUN 2000-40	
Yield (kWh/kW)	909	876

Table 9: summary of Longi and Maxeon panels in the final offer

Among the offers we received, different mounting solutions were proposed: adhesive solution with no inclination (flat mounting), adhesive south-oriented with 10° inclination angle, ballast system south-oriented with 10° inclination angle and ballast system delta configuration east-west with 10° inclination angle. Even though the adhesive solution is lighter in weight and cheaper in price, the review committee suggests the installation should avoid adhesive and flat mounting because of potential reduction in the annual generation or system lifetime caused by: (i) accumulation of dust not being able to naturally wash off the panels, (ii) water and frost-defrost cycles that may jeopardize sealing between the frame and the solar cells over the long term. In addition, adhesive solution with 10-year warranty being a newer and less proven solution poses uncertainty for long term (25 year) robustness, while the ballast system is a simpler, tried, and tested solution and more widely used. Based on this, we decided to go ahead with ballast mounting solutions.

Figure 36: Solar panels in east-west orientation on "delta" ballast mounting in Nobelparken (provided by the contractor)

3.4.3.2 Static analysis

Based on the regulation in Denmark, if the change of static load to the roof is great than 5% with the installation of solar panels, a building permit is required. For this purpose and to evaluate if the roof is strong enough to support the additional weight from the PV system, we hired a structural engineering consultant Artelia.

Since the buildings were old, it was initially difficult to find details about the roof construction, which was required for the analysis. The consultant had contacted FEAS and contractors who had previously worked on the original design of the building, but not enough details were found. We then reached out to the municipality's archive to search for the details on the materials used in the building, with the permission from FEAS. It turned out that those details were still not enough for the engineering consultant to make a conclusion, so a destructive investigation was carried out to find out the exact insulation layers on the rooftop and their thickness. In the meantime, 1komma5 Danmark provided simulated results on the weight of the actual system. Based on the input, it was determined the solar panels can be placed as illustrated in the section view (red area indicates that solar panels are allowed, 0.5 m from each side of the fall line) without causing more than 5% change to the structural load of the roof. Figure 37 illustrates the area where solar panels can be installed. It is therefore concluded that application for building permit is not necessary if the panels are installed on the area that are allowed by the statics analysis.

Figure 37: Areas on the rooftops where solar panels are allowed (taken from Artelia's report dated 14/06/2024)

3.4.3.3 Roof renovation evaluation

The buildings in Nobelparken were built in the early 2000s, and according to the agreement between FEAS and UEF, UEF must bear the cost associated with the PV system having to be removed and re-established (in whole or in part) if the roof needs to be replaced or renovated in the future. Alternatively, if UEF wishes to repair the rooftop (e.g. getting new asphalt layer) earlier than the end of the lifetime, UEF is expected to pay for the early repair. Based on a recent investigation conducted by a roof specialist appointed by FEAS, it is expected that the asphalt layer on the rooftop has another 10-15 years lifetime. So, there are two options faced by UEF: (1) pay now to get new asphalt layer so it will not require the system to be dismantled and reconnected in 15 years, or (2) wait till the end of lifetime of the current asphalt layer and pay for the removal and re-installation of the PV system when FEAS carries out roof repairing/renovation in 15 years' time.

A preliminary analysis of costs based on results from Internet search and a quotation from a roof specialist suggest that it will make more economic sense to go for option 2.

3.4.3.4 Insurances

One of the challenges during the negotiation with FEAS is regarding fire and liability insurance. UEF is asked to take on liability insurance, in case the roof is damaged because of the installation. The liability insurance should also cover any damages caused to the buildings or people, in case, for example, a panel is blown away during a storm after installation. The final solution to this challenge is that we UEF takes on insurance to cover the solar panels as well as the liability insurance. The insurance together with the administration fee of the insurance agent cost around 10,000 kr per year.

3.4.3.5 Execution

Installation of the solar panels took place in the summer of 2024. Mounting of the panels was carried out in an extended period from end of June to early August, due to shortage of manpower during the summer break. By the end of August 2024, all the solar panels were mounted and connected. The installation was officially connected to the grid in September.

From September 2024 onwards, we have been monitoring the performance of the installation and investigating whether the amount of electricity produced matches the simulation result. During this process, we discovered some connection error made by the contractors, which caused the production on one of the building rooftops to be lower than the expected value. This problem was eventually solved by technician in Feb 2025. Another incident in March 2025 uncovered another connection error, which led to the shutdown of the installation for a month from mid-March. The problem was later fixed by technician in late April.

We believe there are no further connection errors with the installation.

Figure 38 below shows the completed installation.

Figure 38: Completed solar photovoltaic installation
(left: on building 1 with Longi panels, right: on building 2 with Maxeon panels).

In August 2025, monitoring system set-up is completed in the Aarhus demonstration site. The monitoring system comprised of 4 irradiance sensors and 1 air temperature sensor, to track real-time weather. The 4 irradiance sensors are faced upwards and downwards, aligning the direction of the solar panels installed on the rooftop. All sensors are

connected to Huawei SmartLogger, which allowed us to integrate these EMI (Environmental Monitoring Instrument) devices in the FusionSolar app. This ensures that we can download and view the environmental data and the electricity production data from the installation at the same time. With these data, we are able to monitor whether the solar photovoltaic plant is producing as much electricity as expected. Figure 39 below shows the placement of the sensors.

Figure 39: Placement of sensors.

AURORA project partner QPV has access to these data and calculates the performance ratio of the installation.

3.4.4 Timeline

A Gantt chart for activities is attached here.

	2022	2023												2024											
Month	1-12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Business model development and legal framework finalization*																									
Cooperative formation (founding meetings and registration)																									
Information and communication campaign																									
Crowdfunding (reservation of shares)																									
Roof statics analysis																									
Contacting contractors for offers																									
Evaluation of contractor offers and decision																									
Collecting funding from the members of the cooperative																									
Infrastructure development and continuous monitoring (including getting building permit, if required)																									

3.4.5 Local dissemination and communication

A series of communication and dissemination activities have taken place to engage the community. From the start of project AURORA, 3 public meetings were held in March 2022, December 2022, November 2023, respectively. In these public meetings, we communicated with the participants the idea of energy communities, discussed the rules of energy cooperative (which later were incorporated into the founding statutes), and showed the preliminary economic analysis. On average, these public meetings have 20 participants each.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036418.

Communication and dissemination of the energy community also took place in forms of public discussions. In these events, a particular theme relevant to energy was discussed, e.g. independence from Russian gas (public discussion in April 2022) or citizens' role in the green transition (roundtable discussion in May 2023). Each of these events attracted between 30-40 participants. In addition to public discussions, we also used local network meetings and conferences as opportunities for communication and dissemination. Some examples of the events include: the citizen science network meeting in AU (August 2022), the Smart Energy Systems conference in Copenhagen (September 2023) and the annual iClimate workshop (November 2022 and October 2023). In March 2024, we participated in a local crowdfunding dinner together with other initiatives to further engage communities outside the university.

Moreover, we distributed flyers and held exhibitions at students' events, such as the Commencement Fair in 2023 and the International Student Fair (October 2022). We also made presentations at various courses in different engineering departments through the fall semester in 2022. All of these events were well attended by students.

In addition to offline activities, we made effort to engage communities through online activities. Activities on social media is constant and regular, so here we emphasize a few highlighted activities. In September 2022, we recorded an episode for the HERfrequency podcast¹ to talk about the AURORA project and the effort to set up an energy community. Together with the communications department at AU, a media campaign was carried out between October and November in 2023, which includes a video² on AU's official YouTube channel and various posts on AU's official LinkedIn page. A press release³ was released in Jan 2024 after the solar cooperative is officially registered and the agreements were successfully signed, which then led to an interview with the regional newspaper TV2Østjylland⁴. In February 2024, we collaborated with the Danish Society of Engineers to host a webinar⁶ themed "Rooftop Solar and Energy Communities in the Danish Green Transition".

After the photovoltaic system was installed, more communication and dissemination activities took place. For example, we attended the national Climate People's Meeting in Middelfart, Denmark from 29th to 31st August with a stand at the exhibition. In October 2024 and March 2025, we held hands-on activities to engage community members and AU students, where they solder and assemble their solar cells. A few other communication and dissemination activities took place, including but not limited to visits to the UEF installation, joint-workshop with local organizations such as Vedvarende Energi and Climate Justice Group.

It is worth mentioning that UEF became a case study for another EU research project ACCTING. Members of the solar cooperative were interviewed by researchers from the ACCTING project, and we attended dedicated workshops and were featured on their website⁷. In March 2025, UEF was highlighted as an inspiring case at the Aarhus University MatchPoint conference.

It should be noted that some of these meetings and conferences overlap with purposes of work packages 1, 4 and 5.

¹ HER Frequency Podcast Episode 18 - AURORA H2020 Energy Project is Cutting Edge Innovative!, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U16gFRms594>

² Andelsprojekt Aurora er solceller på tagene af AU's bygninger, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RQ5uPPA4F5E>

³ Andelsbaserede solceller på tagene af Aarhus Universitet skal levere strøm til universitet, <https://www.uef.dk/news/Andelsbaserede-solceller-paa-tagene-af-aarhus-universitet>

⁴ Nyt projekt: Nu kan studerende købe sig ind i den grønne omstilling, <https://www.tv2ostjylland.dk/aarhus/nyt-projekt-nu-kan-studerende-koebe-sig-ind-i-den-groenne-omstilling>

⁵ Studerende køber solceller, <https://www.tv2ostjylland.dk/arkiv?date=2024-02-05&clip=9046645c-7151-4dfe-8c69-a95d1a099f4a>

⁶ Link to recordings of the webinar: https://videos.ida.dk/playlist/dedicated/1_mxqra9eh/1_3b7r0ujz

⁷ <https://accting.eu/accting-case-study-empowering-students-in-the-energy-transition/>

3.4.6 Operation after the end of the project

Since UEF is registered as an independent association with its own statutes and board of directors, its operation is not affected by the end of project AURORA. The statutes of UEF specifies how it should be operated with elected board of directors from annual general assemblies.

The PV system will continue to produce energy, which will be consumed by Aarhus University. The agreement between UEF and AU is recently extended to cover until August 2028.

As of July 2025, together with AURORA, UEF board of directors and volunteers are developing a maintenance plan for the solar power plant.

3.4.7 Summary

The local solar energy facility has made significant progress, from initial idea to final realisation as a cooperative. The “prosumer via third party” framework is explored and adopted, and the solar cooperative is officially established. We have eventually secured 876 shares from 120 members. The solar PV installation was completed in 2024. Continuous monitoring of production has uncovered connection errors, which were subsequently rectified. The monitoring system was set up in August 2025 to track environmental data such as irradiance and temperature. As the facility is operated and managed by UEF, the ending of AURORA will have minimal impact on the future operation of the solar power plant.

3.5 Demonstrator Site – Forest of Dean, United Kingdom

3.5.1 Introduction

Forest of Dean District Council declared a Climate Emergency in December 2018 and aims to make the District carbon neutral by 2030. The Council is strongly committed to delivering The Climate Emergency Strategy and Action Plan 2022-2025 and the AURORA project contributes to this effort to reduce carbon across the district. At the start of the AURORA project there were a range of opportunities and options for the choice of location of the solar PV power plant. An assessment of buildings owned by the Forest of Dean District Council was made, both those owner-occupied and those with tenants. Forest of Dean District Council political leaders and senior management and leadership team were strongly committed to decarbonisation of its own buildings, following the success of a solar PV rooftop installation at the main Council Offices.

At the same time the Climate Emergency Officer was working in partnership with Freedom Leisure, the not-for-profit organisation who manages the operation of all leisure centres in our district, in relation to decarbonisation of Lydney Leisure Centre. This partnership also included the co-located school, The Dean Academy, which is owned by The Athelstan Trust. A green Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) had been signed by all parties, committing to work together on sustainability and carbon reduction projects. Therefore, it was agreed to look at the potential for the AURORA project solar PV power plant to be installed on the roofs of the leisure centre and school.

Business models for community energy were considered, and three main models were evaluated for their strengths, weaknesses, difficulty in setting up and operating, and ability to deliver within the timescales of the AURORA project. The three models were a Community Benefit Society, a Co-operative Society and Community Municipal Investments (Bonds). Decision making and progress took place as follows:

- AURORA FoDDC Project Board agreed the community investment model (model 2 out of three structures) would be the best approach. This model involved working with an existing community solar energy co-operative partner to complete technical tasks, contract development, installation and operation of the community share offer (April 2022)
- FoDDC Cabinet Briefing, Cabinet agreed that model 2 was the preferred approach (May 2022)
- Lydney Leisure & Dean Academy Energy Group considered the business models and also agreed model 2 was the best way forward (Jun 2022)
- Draft Expression of Interest invitation was developed jointly between FoDDC and the Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE) colleagues (Jul-Oct 2022)
- AURORA FoDDC Project Board agreed and approved the Expression of Interest approach (Oct 2022)

Since then, with advice taken from procurement professionals, external renewable energy organisations and Publica colleagues it was felt that the Expression of Interest invitation becoming a formal tender on the procurement portal was not the right approach. An alternative approach taken to gain understanding of capabilities of local co-operatives and evaluate prospective partners' fit with AURORA project requirements would be more appropriate.

In partnership with CSE, colleagues from FoDDC heard presentations from three local providers and clarified their business models and compatibility with the AURORA project aims. The AURORA FoDDC Project Board, together with our Energy Community (Forest Community Energy) agreed to work with Big Solar Co-op as the energy co-operative partner in March 2023 and a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) agreement was signed between FoDDC and Big Solar Co-op in April 2023.

The intention is to get local people (through Forest Community Energy and engagement with the wider community in the Forest of Dean) to buy a share or multiple shares in Big Solar Coop (which is a national cooperative), giving them an opportunity to invest in community solar in the Forest of Dean. The financial model, due to administrative activities, is only viable at a minimum share price of £100 and the shares will be managed by Sharenergy, the parent organisation

of Big Solar Co-op. By investing in a larger portfolio this will enable local people to invest in their local scheme and they will also benefit from the risk of investment being spread over a wider portfolio of projects. This enables our share offer to pay an annual dividend to all shareholders at a generous 5% interest rate or 2% above the Bank of England base rate of higher. As of 13th July 2025, this rate is 4.25%, therefore share interest would be 6.25%

A strength of this approach is the development and capacity building of our energy community, working together with Big Solar Co-op. Members, volunteers and local community members involved in the activities of Forest Energy Community are able to learn how to deliver community solar projects and how to prepare legal documents and agreements, seek permissions and approvals and manage an installation.

This capacity building will ensure that Forest Energy Community members will be able to promote community solar across the district, understand how to assess a building's potential for rooftop solar, be able to work up designs and become skilled in host site liaison. Once complete, the Lydney installation as a case study or blueprint can be replicated on other leisure centres, schools, community centres and village halls across the district. This is the legacy we aspire to after the AURORA project has been completed.

3.5.2 Conceptual design

3.5.2.1 Location

Lydney Leisure Centre is located in the town of Lydney, in the southern part of Forest of Dean District. It provides facilities including a swimming pool, sports hall, a gym and programme of fitness classes and swimming lessons. It is located at Church Road, Lydney, Gloucestershire, GL15 5DZ. Co-ordinates: 51.721, -2.536. The Dean Academy is a secondary school for students aged 11-16 offering a full curriculum of subjects. It is co-located with the leisure centre, with the same address.

The aerial view in Figure 40 shows the location of both sites and the immediate area.

Figure 40: Freedom Leisure Lydney and The Dean Academy (source: Google Maps)

An initial site visit and study of the site proposed the use of the roof of the swimming pool building, (understood at early stages of this project to be owned by Forest of Dean District Council) and four buildings owned by The Athelstan Trust, the administration building, the sports hall, the two-story classrooms building and the Design and Technology (DT)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036418.

building. It was estimated that all five roofs together could achieve approximately 200 kW. Figure 41 below shows the initial preferred buildings in scope for the AURORA project.

Figure 41: Freedom Leisure Lydney and The Dean Academy – preferred buildings 2022 (source: FoDDC)

3.5.2.2 Installation details

Since Big Solar Co-op started working on the project, things have progressed with pace. In April 2023 presentations and meetings took place with the senior managers of the leisure centre and school, and details of the installation were discussed. A detailed site visit took place and the technical lead from Big Solar Co-op met with facilities management colleagues on site and looked at electric connection points, configuration and location of wiring across the site and evaluated the potential of the roofs.

The project has been split into two phases, phase 1 being the swimming pool building roof as this has its own meter point, and phase 2 is all other buildings, which feed into a second meter on the school site. From an electricity use point of view, the solar panels can be installed on the optimal roofs and the generated power will be used across the entire school site. Choice of roofs considered shade, orientation, roof construction and type, proximity to electrical connection points and capacity. For phase 2, all buildings on the school site are currently having designs produced and there will be a number of configurations on the table, to best meet the usage requirements. Due to this, the precise designs are taking a little longer.

Figure 42: Lydney Leisure Centre - Solar PV panel design (source: Big Solar Co-op)

The swimming pool roof has been designed for maximum number of panels. This is both for current electricity usage requirements and to be compatible with future projects such as the installation of EV chargers in the car park, battery storage and the replacement of gas boilers with ground or air source heat pumps. Figure 42 above shows the design for the swimming pool roof.

In this proposed design, the estimated total kilowatt peak (kW) installed is 62 kW, with an estimated annual output in kilowatt hours (kWh) of 54,524 kWh.

A single type of PV technology will be used: European ethically sourced panels from Meyer Burger. Their modules are produced in Germany using 100% renewable energy. Their polysilicon is sourced from Germany and Norway. These panels are very high quality and are more expensive than comparable products. They do have a very low degradation rate which over time compensates for much of the added cost.

The majority of the power generated will be used by the leisure centre, purchased at approximately 50% of their current tariff, on a power purchase agreement for 30 years. Any solar energy that is not used on site is exported to the grid, sold at the wholesale energy price.

In July 2023 a full electrical survey was completed on all school buildings and as a result, a new, larger design was proposed for the school. This new array would have approximately 246 kW and an estimated output of 222,012 kWh/a. Figure 43 below shows the new design, covering a total of 8 buildings.

Building No.	Building Name	Type of Roof, Material, Age
1	Sports Hall	Metal Roof – built in 1971
2	PE Block	Flat, felt, resurfaced in 2016
3	Science Block	Flat, felt, resurfaced in 2016
4	Science Block	Flat, felt, resurfaced in 2016
5	Admin / Reception	Concrete Tiles – built in 2006
6	G Block	Concrete Tiles – built in 1985
7	E Block	Concrete Tiles – built in 1985
8	C/A Block	Concrete Tiles – built in 1971

Figure 43: The Dean Academy - Solar PV panel design (source: Big Solar Co-op)

3.5.3 Implementation and current status

The solar PV facility could not be implemented yet, due to delays in business model selection and the decision-making process for selecting a community energy co-operative partner in 2023. A positive aspect has been that Freedom Leisure, The Dean Academy and The Athelstan Trust have been continually committed and supportive of this project and keen to progress. The development phase has taken far longer and complexities around the ownership of the buildings and land have taken time to understand. This was important so that each contract and agreement was signed by the correct party, and all applications and approvals were sought, and by whom. During 2023 it came to light upon receiving copies of additional lease documents (previously unseen), that The Athelstan Trust owned the swimming pool building and FoDDC leases it. This resulted in new legal agreements being drawn up to reflect this, and an additional 'Deed of Variation' document.

Heavy workload and capacity of lawyers representing both FoDDC and The Athelstan Trust has meant significant delays in the finalisation and signing of the legal agreements. As such, the local share offer promotion is on hold, awaiting legal document signing before launch. With the 300 kW size design, we are looking to raise approximately £175,000 for this project. These delays have also meant that our grid connection permit for the swimming pool roof (approved in August 2023) is now due for renewal and under current UK rules, this can only be renewed once. Therefore, we are working hard to progress to the point where we are able to set installation dates for the swimming pool roof as soon as possible.

3.5.4 Timeline and planning

The timeline for the installation of the project, led by Big Solar Co-op is as follows:

- Commercial proposal, Exclusivity agreement and Letter of Authority sent - completed
- Commercial proposal accepted - completed
- Exclusivity agreement and Letter of Authority signed and returned - completed
- Arrange next steps online call - completed
- Organise structural survey of roof for swimming pool - completed
- Apply for grid connection - G99 for swimming pool - completed
- DfE installation and lease approval for swimming pool – in progress
- Engage installer - completed
- Land registry searches - completed
- Get copy lease agreement - completed
- Create land registry compliant plan - completed
- Draw up legal agreements and send - completed
- Existing electrical survey - completed
- Arrange purchase of panels/inverters/mounting/sundries for swimming pool – completed
- Pre-start visit for swimming pool – completed
- Engage installer - completed
- Organise structural survey for school – completed
- Apply for grid connection – G99 for school – completed

The final steps that still remain are:

- Pre-start visit for school – to do
- Submission of RAMS to client - to do
- Site set up – to do
- Arrange purchase of panels/inverters/mounting/sundries for school – to do
- Schedule installation date with host sites – to do

- Installation begins – target date August 2025 for swimming pool, August-October 2025 for school
- Mid installation site visit – to do
- Witness testing and commissioning – to do
- Insurance handover - to do
- Schedule post installation site visit with client – to do
- Set up billing schedule with host – to do
- Arrange maintenance schedule (cleaning, repairs etc.) - to do

In July 2025 the HM Treasury intervened to block the Department for Education (DfE) from approving all Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) for solar installations in schools - treating them as public borrowing now requiring government approval. We asked our local MP, Matt Bishop to write to the Government to ask whether the restriction applies to Lydney Leisure Centre. The UK Government confirmed in writing that we can proceed, saying:

“The government is currently considering the fiscal and budgetary impacts of the potential borrowing associated with power purchase agreements (PPA) projects of this kind. We are working to provide clarity as soon as we can on whether these projects can go ahead. The application by the Athelstan Trust in respect of the Dean Academy will not be impacted by this, as the leisure centre operator will enter the PPA agreement rather than the academy trust”.

A version of the legal document marked ‘final version’ will be sent to the DfE and consent will follow. Unfortunately, the grid connection permit has lapsed and needs to be renewed. With these further obstacles cleared, we expect to install by November 2025, shortly before the end of the project.

In respect of The Dean Academy, during this pause on consents, we will continue to work with the DfE to resolve the financial risks and liabilities the UK Government is concerned with, as these risks lie with Big Solar Co-op in the legal agreements, not the school or educational trust. We are optimistic that in time, but after the end date of AURORA, we will succeed in obtaining DfE consent and install on the school roofs too.

3.5.5 Local dissemination and communication

Following some initial citizen research meetings (community drop ins) in 2022 (reported in D4.2), interested residents were invited to the first “FECI meeting” in December 2022. This meeting was attended by 6 local residents and the AURORA FoD team fed back the key findings from the drop ins and the plan for the further development of the energy community.

Figure 44: a slide taken from the December 2022 online event which shows our plan for the AURORA project in relation to our Energy Community.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036418.

Seven workshops followed in the early part of 2023 to Spring 2023. These workshops were primarily dedicated to choosing an appropriate business model for our energy community. It was during this time that the energy community and AURORA FoD team decided to work with Big Solar Coop to progress the solar PV business models.

Figure 45: Photos from the initial FECl workshops. The image on the right shows some of the diagrams to highlight the key aspects of working with Big Solar Coop and what the business model would look like

In the Spring-Summer of 2023, the Forest Energy Community Initiative (which then renamed to Forest Community Energy) had regular monthly meetings online and in person. These meetings were focused on the legal constitution of the FCE energy community. However, in this time, there was a noticeable decrease in the number of active members in the group. This was due to the local elections in the Forest of Dean meaning that a lot of our active volunteers were elected as cabinet members in the council. This took away their available time to commit to FCE in the way they had before.

Following this decrease in engagement, and a change in AURORA FoD staff team, a decision was taken to hold off on legally constituting the group and focus on widening our engagement to recruit more members to the group, planning for more WP1 and WP4 activities to feed into our civic roadmap. These meetings are therefore classed as WP1 citizen research meetings and reported in D4.2 and D4.1 in relation to our civic roadmap.

As we progress the solar PV installations, we will begin to focus again on using these meetings to progress WP3 activities. For example, in January we held a meeting that focused on developing a plan for promoting our local share offer, developing a list of local networks and stakeholders to promote through.

In total, we have counted 13 WP3 engagement events, reaching up to 20 citizens each (although attendance fluctuated between a minimum of 3 citizens to 20).

3.5.6 Operation after the end of the project

The lease and power purchase agreement signed between Big Solar Co-op and the building owners and tenants will be for a period of 30 years. During this 30 year period, Big Solar Co-op will operate and maintain the solar PV array, insure it and administer the community share scheme (via their parent organisation Sharenergy). This approach ensures the effective continuation of the installation after the end of the AURORA Project.

Forest Community Energy has identified all required Directors for the Board and by September 2025 will be registered as a Community Benefit Society. This means that Forest Community Energy will be able to continue with replication opportunities beyond AURORA either independently or in collaboration with others.

3.5.7 Summary

In summary, this complex project has made progress to the implementation stage however, the recent pause by the UK Government on approving solar PPAs and us getting clarification on how this impacts our project has caused further delays. We are optimistic that we have overcome barriers and blocks and have certainty about completion for the Lydney Leisure Centre, with a target installation date of November 2025. Once complete, this community solar installation will provide educational and learning opportunities for students at The Dean Academy and via the community share offer, will provide community support. It will provide a case study and blueprint for potential replication across the district and our energy community. Forest Energy Community will use the learning of the process to implement further solar installations in the district, contributing to carbon reduction and net zero goals.

4 Monitoring, surveillance and operation assessment

The installations implemented in each Demo Site should be well defined and supervised once they are operating. In addition, this definition and supervision should be common to all Demo Site in order to have a unified methodology. This section defined the technical specifications, productivity studies and monitoring system that will be used along the project.

4.1 Technical Specifications

The production of the rooftop solar photovoltaic installation should be able to meet the electricity demand of these buildings according to the time of use. The goal of the installation is to maximize self-consumption on-site, while the surplus energy should be injected back to the electricity grid when the local demand of the building is lower than the production of the solar panels. In addition, the solar PV installation will be made available for scientific research and teaching. In particular, technical data such as electricity produced every hour will be available for interested students and researchers.

For this purpose, technical specifications describe on the basis of the tender for the procurement, construction and commissioning of a 200 kW grid-connected PV plant to be installed on the rooftops of these buildings.

The specifications that concern the common elements with conventional PV plants (PV generators and inverters) and the reception tests of the installation are inspired by the technical documentation prepared in the context of the European project AURORA.

The following section defines an overview of an installation structure adapted to each location.

Figure 46 describes an example of a PV installation structure. This installation can be composed by different generation zones, each of them composed by PV arrays and inverters. Each generation unit is connected to the building electrical grid through the corresponding Connection Point (CP), multiple generation units can share the same CP. The particular configuration of the PV plant can be constituted by a single inverter or by several inverters.

Figure 46: General layout of the PV installation.

For the purposes of this technical specifications, the PV plant is composed of the following elements:

- PV arrays
- DC/AC inverters
- Supporting structure
- Energy meters
- Measurement, monitoring, and data acquisition system

Each corresponding Technical Specification Annex shall contain adapted installation model to each demonstration site, as most sites will be made up for multiple rooftop installation, and provide corresponding information regarding:

- Site outlines, scope and distribution tailored to the final construction planning
- PV array considerations
- Inverter considerations and over dimensioning
- Structural considerations
- LV energy meter considerations
- Monitoring requirements
- Grounding and lightning protection information
- Safety and fire protection requirements
- Warranty requirements
- Bidder PV and Yield information

Each installation will have its own technical specification. The general document is in Annex I. As construction is still in the planning phases for most locations, the Technical Specifications of each Demo Site shall be added and updated with further development.

4.2 Productivity Studies

The objective of the productivity studies is the preliminary theoretical estimation of the energy production of the 200kW rooftop installations across 5 different locations in Europe as part of the AURORA project. The analysis of these studies ends at the connection point to the building to which the installation is connected to.

All the information related to the constitution of the photovoltaic site (location, physical and electrical structure, technical information of the devices used, etc.) should be provided by each individual location. Meteorological data will be obtained from different satellite sources available for the sites. The rest of the information necessary for the realization of this report, such as the loss scenario, the degradation profiles, the simulation models, etc., will be defined by QPV.

Estimating productivity is the first step in the quality control process. Accordingly, these reports provide some considerations for the later steps of this process. Finally, the uncertainty in the estimation of productivity is analysed, in order to obtain different probabilities of meeting the expectations established for the lifetime of facilities.

4.2.1 Simulation Overview

The estimation of the productivity of a PV installation is the result of a calculation made assuming a base case consisting of three different components:

- The temporal evolution of the operating conditions (effective irradiance in the generator plane, $G^{ef}(I)$, and module temperature, T_C), modelled from the meteorological conditions (mainly horizontal global irradiance, $G(0)$, and ambient temperature, T_A), obtained in turn from long-term observations, either direct from meteorological stations on the ground or indirect from satellite images.
- The potential response corresponding to a hypothetical reference system, which considers only the unavoidable losses, i.e. those inherent in the design of the PV system, its location (e.g. due to shadows due to the horizon profile) or the difference between the actual operating conditions and the Standard Measurement Conditions (STC).⁸
- A scenario of expected or permitted losses, which establishes the maximum admissible difference between the yields of the reference system and the actual system to be built.

Therefore, estimating productivity is based on two types of assumptions. On the one hand, those that describe the weather and operating conditions on site. On the other hand, those that describe the constitution of the PV plant and its electrical response. Table 10 summarizes the most relevant assumptions, insofar as they are those that involve the greatest uncertainty.

Table 10: Assumptions that entail a greater degree of uncertainty when estimating the productivity of a PV plant.

Weather conditions	Electrical response of the plant
Solar Irradiance	Photovoltaic generator
<i>Horizontal Irradiance</i>	<i>Effective power at the input of inverter</i>
<i>Irradiance Distribution</i>	<i>Variation of efficiency with $G^{ef}(I)$ and T_C</i>
<i>Fraction of the diffuse</i>	Inverter
Temperature	<i>Efficiency</i>
<i>Ambient temperature evolution T_A</i>	<i>Auxiliary consumption</i>
	Operation
	<i>Soiling</i>
	<i>Degradation</i>

⁸The Standard Measurement Conditions are defined by an effective irradiance incident normally in the plane of the generator, $G^* = 1,000 \text{ W / m}^2$; an operating temperature of the PV modules, $T_C = 25 \text{ C}$ and a spectral distribution characterized by an air mass AM1.5. °

4.2.2 Meteorological Conditions

Meteorological conditions at a site are mainly characterized by horizontal global irradiation, ambient temperature, and wind speed and direction. In general, data sources describing these conditions provide long-term time series (at least 10 years) of different meteorological parameters, including horizontal global irradiance $G(0)$, horizontal diffuse irradiance $D(0)$, ambient temperature T_A , wind speed and direction, atmospheric pressure, humidity, etc., with an hourly resolution. In addition, some data sources provide the Typical Meteorological Year (TMY), which is a collection of actual weather data specially selected on a monthly basis to be consistent with long-term averages for the plant location.

In this study, the simulation of the energy productivity of the system is done with SISIFO, the simulation tool for photovoltaic systems developed at the Solar Energy Institute of the Polytechnic University of Madrid (IES-UPM).

The input meteorological data is a synthetic data of solar irradiation generated with the SISIFO tool with the monthly data obtained from PVGIS. The information necessary for the preparation of this report, such as the loss scenario, simulation profiles, etc., has been defined by the IES-UPM.

4.2.3 Reference System

The reference system is defined by three assumptions:

- The *EMC* power of PV generators at the inverter input is equal to their rated power. In addition, the responses of the generator with irradiance and temperature are adjusted to the corresponding coefficients provided by the manufacturer.
- The efficiency curves of inverters and transformers are those specified in the catalogues of the respective manufacturers.
- The system has none of the so-called avoidable losses.

Therefore, the only energy losses in the reference system are:

- Losses in the PV generator due to the difference between actual operating conditions and *EMC*.
- Direct current to alternating current (DC/AC) conversion losses in the inverter, according to manufacturer information.
- Losses inherent to the design of the PV plant. Specifically, those corresponding to power limitations due to the lack of compatibility between the inverter and the generator (continuous/alternating ratio greater than one, V_{MPP} ⁹ lower than the minimum voltage required for the generation of a given V_{AC} and I_{MPP} greater than the maximum current admitted by the inverter) and shading losses due to the design of the installation itself, like the shadows between structures.

⁹The continuous/alternating ratio refers to the ratio between the *EMC* power of the PV generator and the maximum power that the inverter can receive at its input.

4.2.4 Admissible Losses

In order to facilitate the performance of subsequent quality control tests, it is appropriate to establish a limit for each of the following losses:

- Technical losses:
 - Losses in the PV generator, which cause the actual power (at the input of the inverter) to be less than the nominal value. They are caused by low power of PV modules, degradation induced by exposure to the Sun (*LID*), parameter dispersion, cabling, etc.
 - Aging losses of PV modules due to exposure to the sun. They should be established in consistency with the module manufacturer's warranties. Obviously, these losses do not apply to the first year of operation.
- Losses due to dust and soiling. They are dependent on place and time. In the starting scenario, periodic cleanings are considered as part of the maintenance plan.
- Losses due to unavailability. They are due to the persistence of operating failures due to their late detection or repair.
- From this point on, this global scenario (comprising the evolution of operating conditions, the potential response of the reference system and the allowable loss scenario) will be referred to as the "**base case**". The annual energy yield resulting from this scenario can serve as a basis for the realization of the economic model that will determine the viability and profitability of the project.

4.2.5 Simulation Models

The productivity estimate of a PV installation is calculated as the integral of its power during a given period. The corresponding calculation combines different mathematical algorithms to obtain, first, $G^{eff}(l)$ and T_C from $G(0)$ and T_A and, second, describe the potential response of each element that makes up the PV system: generator and inverter. To perform this calculation, a variety of commercial models and programs are available.

In the same way as other highly specialized PV research centres, QPV does not use commercial programs to carry out this type of exercise, but its own and bankable alternative: SISIFO, which is based on QPV's experience in quality control procedures and whose¹⁰ **results have been validated with real data in a portfolio with more than 150 projects and a total capacity of more than 4 GW**. The mathematical models incorporated in SISIFO have been selected to obtain the best match with the experimental power values measured in these plants. They are advanced models and lead to results that, as will be presented, are practically coincident with those obtained with other commercial tools such as, for example, PVSyst. However, SISIFO offers some significant additional advantages that facilitate the subsequent application of low uncertainty quality control procedures:

- The possibility of adjusting, at any time during the development of the project, the simulation models and their parameters to obtain the best fit to the experimental results for each location and type of PV plant.
- The models used are based solely on the parameters guaranteed by the manufacturers, which allows to maintain the chain of responsibility throughout the project, which is key to identify, allocate and manage risks correctly.
- The possibility of establishing a direct link between the productivity estimates, calculated in the design phase, and the actual performance of the plant, measured in the different field test campaigns and stages of the quality control procedure. This makes it possible to reduce the uncertainty of the estimation and thus improve the predictability of the project.

In any case, to underpin the robustness of the QPV methodology, the results of the simulation carried out with SISIFO are compared with those obtained using PVSyst.

¹⁰ SISIFO is free and available in www.sisifo.info

4.2.6 Degradation

PV modules are the most relevant element when analysing the degradation experienced by a PV plant throughout its life cycle. For crystalline silicon modules, it has been common to consider that their long-term degradation responded to a linear process over time, with annual rates between 0.5%/year and 0.7%/year. For example, a degradation of 12% after 30 years of operation is understood to be equivalent to a linear power loss of 0.6%/year. However, QPV has data on the generation of real facilities with sufficient statistical representativeness that include measurements at intermediate moments and that question that the degradation is linear from the first year¹¹.

An accurate degradation model has a significant effect on the project's long-term production estimates, even if the final warranty given by the manufacturer is maintained. As an example, Figure 47 shows, on the one hand, the evolution of the power following the classic linear assumption from the first year of operation and, on the other hand, two models that consider that the degradation is equally linear but that it does not begin until the fifth year. In addition, one of them considers a minor degradation between years 5 and 15 of operation. The latter model is better suited to the experimental evidence found in the literature and constitutes a recommendation for QPV. The area between the lines constitutes the additional production expected by considering models other than the classic linear and results in an increase of up to 3.0% of the total production at 30 years.

Figure 47: Evolution of the power of the PV modules (in relation to their initial stabilized value) over the years of operation. The green area represents the increase in energy derived from considering the degradation of the module only from the fifth year and not from the first.

It is considered that the elements of the system (support structure, wiring, etc) do not suffer a degradation that significantly affects the productivity of the installation.

¹¹ Conclusions derived from recent studies by the Instituto de Energía Solar de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (IES-UPM) on more than 1300 PV generators in Spain after up to 15 years of operation, by CIEMAT (Toledo-PV, +30 years of operation) and by Fraunhofer-FISE (+100 installations in Germany).

4.2.7 Irradiance evolution

Solar resource assessment for a given site is generally based on the assumption that the long-term average annual solar irradiance of the past is relatively consistent with the "true" climatological value and, therefore, that this value can be used as an estimator of future solar resource availability¹². However, there is growing evidence that the amount of solar radiation striking the Earth's surface is not stable over the years, but experiences significant variations over the decades. Studies looking at long-term measurements of radiation at the Earth's surface suggest that there was a generalized decrease in solar radiation between the 50s and 90s ("global dimming") and, more recently, a partial recovery at many sites ("global clearance"). This evidence is consistent with other independent observations concerning the evolution of day length, temperature ranges and evaporation levels, and other satellite observations.

These variations respond to anthropogenic changes in the Earth's atmosphere, due to the evolution of aerosol emissions derived, on the one hand, from economic development and, on the other, from anti-pollution regulations. As an example, Figure 48 presents simulated solar radiation trends for the periods of (a) "global dimming" (1950–1990) and (b) "global clearance" (1990–2002)¹³.

Given these long-term trends, the question is no longer what is the "true" climatological value, but what will be the best prediction for the evolution of radiation over the next 30 years. An adequate estimate should start from a recent period of time, long enough to filter out the influence of anomalies due to particular years, but at the same time short enough to minimize the influence of past trends¹³. Müller et al. propose to use irradiation data from the last 10 years as a compromise to meet these conditions. That is why, in this report, we have considered this period and not a longer one.

It is worth considering how these trends are expected to evolve in the future. Some studies suggest that further clearance is not expected in industrialized countries, as aerosol levels have stabilized at low values since 2000¹³. On the contrary, a new period of global dimming is not excluded, as rising emissions in Southeast Asia are outpacing declines in the Western world. Moreover, to the extent that these trends are due to anthropogenic emissions, they may change substantially in the future in response to economic growth, energy consumption, or anti-pollution regulations. For what matters here, we will adopt the assumptions of Wild et al. (Figure 48) for each site and will not consider a significant reduction in radiation over the life of the project, but we will include an additional source of uncertainty in the following sections to take into account the possible effects of long-term radiation evolution.

Figure 48: Simulated solar radiation trends for (a) the "global dimming" period (1950–1990) and (b) the "global clearance" period (1990–2002).

¹² Reise C. et al. 2018. Uncertainties in PV System Yield Predictions and Assessments. IEA-PVPS T13-12:2018

¹³ Wild, M, 2009. Global dimming and brightening: A review. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 114

4.2.8 Inter-year variability

Another aspect to consider when calculating the long-term productivity of an installation is the impact of anomalies on climatic parameters or, in other words, the interannual variability of solar irradiation. By definition, this variation is more important annually than when considering the entire project life cycle. For the site of this project, it is calculated from the satellite data provided by PVGIS and is defined as the variability in the annual irradiation that ensures a confidence interval of 95% around the average of the decade.

4.2.9 Uncertainty Estimation

The financial attractiveness of a PV project is evaluated according to two distinct characteristics: profitability and risk. The profitability of the project is associated with the E_{P90} parameter (or probability of a certain risk, behaviour, or event being 90%), which is the most likely value of annual energy production. Then, assuming that the differences between the estimates and the actual values follow a Gaussian distribution, it is possible to derive the project risk from the global uncertainty, σ , that affects energy production. The combination of both values allows to obtain other financial parameters of interest, such as E_{P90} or E_{P99} .

The global uncertainty associated with the estimation of the E_{P50} of a PV plant results from the combination of three different sources of uncertainty: that relating to meteorological databases, σ_{MET} , that relating to the simulation of the power response of the system, σ_{SIM} , and that relating to the characteristics of the PV system itself, σ_{STC} . Table 7 describes the calculation of uncertainty for the first year of operation and for a period of 30 years.

Table 11: Main sources of uncertainty affecting the calculation of the E_{P50} of the project.

Uncertainty Source	Year 1 (%)	30 Years (%)
Meteorological data, σ_{MET}		
Database, σ_{DB}		4.5
Year-on-year variability, σ_{IV}	4.2	0.8 ^a
Long-term radiation evolution, σ_{LT}	0.05	1.5 ^b
Temperature database, σ_{AT}		1.0
Simulation of potential response, σ_{SIM}		
Soiling, σ_{DU}		1.0
Calculation of operating conditions, σ_{OC}		2.5 ^c
System Potential Response, σ_{PR}		1.0 ^d
Characteristics STC σ_{STC}		
Initial characteristics STC, σ_{CH}		2.8 ^e
Degradation, σ_{AG}	N.A.	3.0 ^f
Total	7.4	7.0

The following comments are pertinent below:

- As a base case, interannual variability is 4.2% for a single year ($k=2$) and 0.8% for a 30-year period is considered.
- As shown in Section 4.2.7, solar radiation is subject to decadal cycles and other long-term trends, due to atmospheric composition (emissions of NO_x , SO_x , emissions from volcanoes...). The available literature shows that the magnitude of these trends varies by location lower bounds of a 95% confidence interval, considering a Gaussian distribution. The expected change after N years can then be estimated as an

invariable mean value and a standard deviation that increases over time, at a rate of 0.05%/year. For a period of 30 years, a maximum uncertainty of 1.5% results.

- c) SISIFO includes models that decompose horizontal global radiation into its diffuse and direct components, which consider the anisotropic nature of diffuse radiation, and which include the effect of dirt on the angular response of PV generators. The estimation of the uncertainty of this step is derived from the comparison of the estimated values with the values measured in several well-maintained PV plants. This term also considers the uncertainty in the calculation of the operating temperature of the generator.
- d) This component includes possible differences between the actual and theoretical yields of PV modules. Studies for silicon modules suggest considering a 1% uncertainty for this point (de la Parra et al. 2017).
- e) This component includes the possible differences between the actual and nominal values of the equipment: peak power, coefficients of variation with temperature and irradiance and degradation by initial exposure (*LID*) of the PV modules, efficiency and monitoring of the maximum power point (*MPP*) of the inverter, auxiliary consumption, transformer efficiency...
- f) In addition to the degradation profile presented in section 4.2.6, a standard deviation of 0.1%/year, cumulative over time, is considered. For a period of 30 years, this leads to a maximum uncertainty value of 3.0%.

Next, it should be noted that **this scenario of uncertainty can be improved**. The application of an Advanced Quality Control Procedure (AQAP) in a PV project is commonly used to ensure the design, quality and execution of the plant. This procedure entails executing field tests during the initial phases of the installation targeting each source of uncertainty, thus reducing the span of the uncertainty distribution. For instance, in order to target the uncertainty due to soiling, a soiling sensor might be installed and then the loss due to soiling is monitored under real conditions. The in-field measurements are then translated into a clearer and more precise prediction models of the installation. Thus, the results of the AQAP can be used to reduce the uncertainty associated with the long-term productivity of the plant and, consequently, the risks associated with the investment. In other words, AQAP can be understood as part of the project's risk management strategy.

Table 8 shows how the application of to all phases of the project reduces **uncertainty** by 33% for the first year and **by more than 50% for a period of 30 years**, resulting in an **increase of 5.3%** in E_{P90} and 10.4% in E_{P99} .

Table 12: Main sources of uncertainty that affect the calculation of the E_{P50} of the project, after the application of the AQAP of the IES-UPM.

Uncertainty Source	Year 1 (%)	30 Years (%)
<i>Meteorological data, σ_{MET}</i>		
Database, σ_{DB}	2.2	
Year-on-year variability, σ_{IV}	4.2	0.8
Long-term radiation evolution, σ_{LT}	0.05	0.05
Temperature database, σ_{AT}	0.5	
<i>Simulation of potential response, σ_{SIM}</i>		
Soiling, σ_{DU}	0.5	
Calculation of operating conditions, σ_{OC}	1.0	
System Potential Response, σ_{PR}	0.5	
<i>Characteristics CEM, σ_{CEM}</i>		
Initial characteristics EMC, σ_{CH}	0.5	
Degradation, σ_{AG}	N.A.	N.A.
Total	4.9	3.3

As an example, Figure 49 presents the probability distribution of the annual productivity estimate of a PV installation together with the evolution of the main indicators used for project financing (E_{P90} and E_{P99}), before and after the application of the AQAP.

Figure 49: Probability function of the estimation of annual productivity of a PV plant and main statistical indicators used in the financing of projects, before (blue) and after (green) the application of an AQAP.

4.2.10 Bibliography

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4.3 Monitoring system

This section describes the monitoring specifications for PV installations in the frame of the European project AURORA. The objective of the monitoring system is to collect the necessary data from the different elements of these installations to perform management and supervision tasks. This data will be available remotely in a way that allows energy community management and main O&M actions remotely. In addition, its use for educational or research tasks is also considered. The monitoring system will be simple and replicable, as well as low cost to have the smallest impact on return on investment of the installations.

4.3.1 Infrastructure description

Figure 50 describes an example of the constitution of the PV installation. It is formed by different generation zones, each of them composed by PV arrays and inverters. Each generation zone is characterized by the fact that it is a set of generation elements that are connected to the electrical grid at the same point Connection Point (CP). This CP is usually a physical connection inside the building where the installation is located. Moreover, a generation zone is usually installed on a rooftop. For example, if a demo site has three rooftops, these will be connected to the building at three different electrical points. Thus, each point must have its own accounting of the energy produced, considering three different generation zones.

Figure 50: General layout of a demo site PV installation.

The particular configuration of each generation zone can be constituted by a single inverter or by several inverters.

Figure 51 shows a general layout of a generation zone with multiple generation units (PV array and inverter), a low-voltage meter and a connection point. This structure will be defined in the technical specifications of each installation. All these elements are the responsibility of the Contractor, except LV meter. This meter is provided by QPV, its wiring and installation is the responsibility of the Contractor.

Figure 51: General layout of a demo site generator zone.

The main operating conditions (G^{ef} and T_C)¹⁴ are measured by reference modules. These modules are, in general, of the same technology as the generator. They are calibrated with a reference standard so that their measurements are indicative of the values of the operating conditions. Moreover, they are installed with the same tilt as the generator, in order to have the same irradiation conditions. Therefore, there is a reference module for each combination technology-tilt. This is indicated in the Technical Specifications as:

48) *The sensors for measuring the effective incident irradiance on the photovoltaic modules, G^{ef} , and their operating cell temperature, T_C , will be reference models of the same technology as the rest of the installation.*

One reference module per inclination and technology is best practice. However, the possibility of placing only one module per inclination could be considered to reduce installation costs.

The physical module is provided by the Contractor. The module is calibrated by QPV. The electronics device to measure the operating conditions variables, together with external box and power supply, are provided by QPV. Electrical power cables and communication cables from the reference module electronics to the monitoring box are provided by the Contractor. Figure 52 shows a conceptual example of the reference module installation together with the generators.

Figure 52: General layout of a generator zone with reference modules.

¹⁴ <https://www.qpv.es/en/news/operating-conditions>

The monitoring system is in charge of collecting and recording the data of the entire installation. It is the equivalent of a SCADA system on a PV plant, but on a smaller scale and simplified. The main set of variables to be collected are:

- Operating conditions: Information from the reference module, as explained before.
- DC operation: Electrical and energy information from the PV array (inverter input).
- AC operation: Electrical and energy information from the inverter output.
- Generation Zone operation: Electrical and energy information from the generation zone output.

This information is measured by different devices. With the aim of reducing the monitoring requirements, the measurement device types are reduced to three:

- Reference Module device: Measures the operating conditions.
- Inverter: Inverters measure their input (DC operation) and output (AC operation).
- LV meter: Measures the Generation Zone operation, ranging from electrical variables to the energy variables. It records the total energy flow that passes through and is mainly used for tasks such as compensation or energy billing.

The information generated by these devices is concentrated in a monitoring box. This box contains the required network devices and a data logger. In addition, it has internet connection. Figure 53 shows a conceptual scheme of the installation together with the monitoring system. The communication cables from each measurement device to the monitoring box is required. These cables depend on the communication protocol. Two protocols are considered:

- RS485: Two wires cables to implement a communication bus.
- TCP/IP Ethernet: Network cables in point-to-point configuration.

In both cases, data are transferred through Modbus protocol.

Figure 53: General layout of a generator zone with reference modules and full monitoring proposal.

The monitoring box has a data logger which implements the data acquisition. This data logger is an embedded computer with open software that consults every device of the installation gathering the required information. The monitoring box has internet connection to export data to remote data bases or cloud. This connection and the local network are managed by a local router with the ability to create VPN. The monitoring box requires local energy supply.

It is composed of low consumption devices, with the total consumption being lower than 100W for the entire box. The demo site will be used as the energy source; thus, the monitoring box should be connected in the generation zone output before the LV meter (consumptions are considered as generation reduction).

The energy supply and communication cables are provided by the Contractor. The communication capacity of the inverters and LV meters is defined in the Technical Specifications. The monitoring box is provided by QPV. The internet connection is provided by the Contractor or the building owner. In case that this is not possible, the possibility of working with a radio connection (GPRS, 3G, Long Wi-Fi) will be studied. It must be taken into account that these costs will affect the O&M cost of the installation.

Internet connection is a requirement for the project. Information must be extracted in order to know the energy produced and to do remote maintenance. In general, building networks and their internet connection are quite stable at present. Considering this, it is possible to implement a virtual data logger. It can be implemented outside of the installation in a remote computer or even on a virtual machine in a cloud. The remote implementation of this data logger can be one for each installation or even for the whole project. Figure 54 shows a conceptual example of this possibility.

Figure 54: General layout of a generator unit with reference modules and remote monitoring proposal.

This proposal has the following advantages and disadvantages:

- Advantages:
 - Reduce number of electronic devices for generation zone.
 - Reduce local maintenance, both hardware and software.
 - Updates are simple, can be done remotely and are the same for the whole project.
- Disadvantage:
 - Loss of connection can cause loss of information. During communication outage data is not recorded, thus, this period of data is lost and cannot be analysed. On the other hand, the energy is always recorded by the LV meter, allowing the energy quantification for compensation or energy billing.

In this configuration, QPV develops, installs and configures the remote data logger. In the case of deploying a remote physical machine, this machine will also be provided by QPV. If a virtual machine is used, it will be provided by the cloud tenant.

4.3.1.1 Additional monitoring considerations

In order to increase the data robustness, data storage capability can be added to the inverters. This functionality would perhaps be excessive if a local data logger is installed. However, it would have more sense if the remote data logger option is chosen. It should be noted how this functionality is specifically implemented by the inverter manufacturer, since in many cases it implies additional equipment with higher costs. This functionality would be provided by the Contractor.

Other devices can be included in the monitoring system. An example of these devices are meteorological stations or air quality sensors. These stations can be included in the Technical Specifications proposal or can be already installed. QPV will configure these devices inside the monitoring system. The energy supply and communication cables are provided by the Contractor.

4.3.2 Monitoring adjustments

The structure of the monitoring system and its elements have been proposed following the objectives of the project. For the specific implementation of each installation, the following issues should be defined or clarified:

- Communication type: It depends on the communication protocol (RS485 or IP). At the same time, the protocol depends on the distance and cost to be assumed.
- Local or remote data logger.
- Inverter data storage capacity.
- Additional devices to be included in the monitoring system.
- Internet connection and remote data storage. During the project, QPV can supply cloud storage, but an alternative should be found after the project ends.

These elements depend on the layout and distribution of the generation zones, as well as the existing elements. Thus, these decisions will be different for each demo site, generating a different monitoring system for each one.

4.3.3 Data management and visualization

The proposed monitoring system aims simple and standard data management, which is easily exportable and adaptable to local requirements. This approach will help with rapid installation during the project activity and its transfer to the entities at the end of the project, which will maintain it from that moment on.

All installations will require external access, preferably through the use of VPN. This is necessary for remote maintenance and visualization of the operation by users. Taking this into account, data logging can be done in 2 ways:

- a) Using a local physical machine. This allows data to be recorded even in situations of loss of communication.
- b) Using a virtual machine. This would be outside the installation and would be accessed through the external connection. In the event of a connection loss, the information would be lost (Current network connections are usually very robust and have availability greater than 99.9%, so it should not be a major problem). This solution is cheaper and easier to maintain.

In both cases, the software used to collect data on this machine will be free software. To carry out this project, Rapid [SCADA](#) has been chosen, due to its rapid learning curve, making it easier for entities to be in charge of its maintenance in the future. Data are recorded in the local machine and will be synchronized to central or local server. This synchronization can be done both to files and databases.

The SCADA installed in the local machine has its own visualization platform. The platform code is part of Rapid SCADA and, thus, open software. It could be integrated into another platform to be presented for external users, as public displays in the demonstrator's premises.

In addition, the data in the external server will be used by the project app so that users can know the operation of their installations.

4.3.4 Monitoring Implementation

As described in previous sections, a monitoring system has been implemented to efficiently collect data from the different photovoltaic installations. This system enables centralized, real-time management of information generated by the various plants, by using different approaches.

The data from demonstrator facilities is gathered by the PVET. PVET Solar Data Analytics is a software-as-a-service (SaaS) platform developed by aurora beneficiary QPV for advanced PV plant analytics, including monitoring, surveillance, and operation assessment. It also enables standardized data collection and performance analysis across sites. The stored data includes key values such as the total energy generated by the plant and total power—critical parameters for tracking operational performance. PVET includes built-in capabilities to generate the photovoltaic data required to calculate key performance indicators (KPIs). This functionality, combined with the incoming data, forms the basis for rigging the plant-level KPI calculation process within PVET.

Finally, the processed data is made available through PVET's APIs, allowing the developer of the Aurora Energy Tracker application and dashboard to directly access the refined information. This facilitates its presentation in the application interface, providing end users with a clear, comprehensible, and accurate experience based on up-to-date information, as shown in Figure 55.

Figure 55: Screenshots of PVET system displaying Aurora data

4.3.4.1 Madrid demonstrator

On the other hand, the PV installation promoted by the Technical University of Madrid in Centro Cultural Palomeras school in Madrid will be completed in the coming weeks. The monitoring system has been designed in dialogue with all the partners involved. Two irradiation cells were installed to monitor and compare the solar irradiance received by two distinct sets of photovoltaic panels located at the plant. These panel sets differ in their tilt angles: one group is inclined at 30°, while the other is inclined at 10°. These solar cells will capture irradiance data representative of both configurations to support the main goal of collecting data on production and operating conditions, to enhance performance evaluation and system optimization.

Different visits have been made to prepare the monitoring system Installation Plan. The first preliminary assessment was carried out on June 26, 2025 to conduct a general site inspection and assess the installation environment, to receive a technical briefing on the panel setups and gain a general understanding of the positioning and logistical considerations for the installation of the irradiation cells. During the second site visit on July 3, 2025, we carried out precise measurements required for the installation, planned the layout for proper mounting of the irradiation cells on the roof and evaluated and defined the cable routing path from the roof to the ground floor where the smart logger is installed. A third visit was necessary, to install the two reference irradiation cells made by manufacturer Seven in their designated rooftop positions, aligned with the respective panel inclinations (30° and 10°). Other tasks accomplished were meeting with Huawei technical support for the configuration of the Smart Logger, connect and integrate the irradiation cells, inverter, and power meter into the Smart Logger system, and obtain credentials and ensure remote access to system data through Huawei's FusionSolar platform for real-time monitoring and analysis

As a summary, two irradiation cells were installed, each aligned with the corresponding inclination of the panel groups (30° and 10°) to ensure representative irradiance measurements. Both cells were connected in parallel and mounted on the rooftop. A combined output cable was routed from the rooftop down to the Huawei Smart Logger, located on the ground floor, for data acquisition and monitoring. The Smart Logger was successfully configured with the support of Huawei representatives, establishing communication between the smart logger, the irradiation cells, the inverter, and the power meter. System credentials were obtained, and data visualization was confirmed via the FusionSolar platform.

4.3.4.1 Evora demonstrator

Monitoring system configuration in the PV installations of Évora in Portugal is still in progress. As the demonstrator has only recently chosen an alternative virtual approach, the monitoring is still being implemented. Once local monitoring will be installed it will be included in the same data flow as other demonstrators.

4.3.4.2 Ljubljana demonstrator

In the specific case of the Ljubljana demonstrator, integration of PV production data into AURORA dashboard and app, has been carried out via data reception through an MQTT server. The system subscribes to the relevant topic, allowing continuous, automated, and uninterrupted reception of data emitted by the plant. This information is stored directly in a storage account, ensuring its availability for various purposes: subsequent analysis, real-time visualization, or the construction of a reliable and accessible historical data record.

Table 13: Ljubljana demonstrator data description.

Period Covered	Variables	Description
2025-05-26 – present	E_{total}	Total energy generated by the installation
	P_{total}	Total power of the installation

Since this plant only provides production data and lacks operating condition variables, PVET automatically generates supporting datasets that are essential for KPI calculation.

The data flow is presented in Figure 56.

Figure 56: Flow diagram of production data collection and display for Ljubljana demonstrator

Figure 57: production and irradiance at Ljubljana demonstrator on a sunny day of August 13, 2025.

4.3.4.3 Aarhus demonstrator

As part of the Aarhus PV facility, QPV has developed a solution for the efficient acquisition of irradiance data. A dedicated connection box has been designed to centralize and facilitate the physical integration of all the reference cells involved, ensuring efficient data collection and its integration into the monitoring system.

Table 14: Aarhus demonstrator data description.

Period Covered	Device	Variables	Description
2024-09-02 - present	String Inverters	PAC	Active power output
		IAC	AC currents per phase
		VAC	AC voltages per phase
		PDC	Total DC power
		VDC	Total DC voltage
		TEMP	Inverter temperature
2025-08-12 - present	EMI	Irradiance	Irradiance measured
		Ambient air temperature	Ambient air temperature

4.3.4.3.1 Dedicated reference cells

As this plant did not initially include operational condition monitoring, a set of reference cells was specifically designed and installed to measure solar irradiance. These devices simulate the behavior of photovoltaic modules, enabling real-time assessment of solar radiation and system performance.

Communication is enabled by an Ethernet-to-RS485 converter (Waveshare model B). It allows integration of serial communication devices into TCP/IP networks. This enables remote acquisition of irradiance data while maintaining centralized management. To power the reference cells and data acquisition devices, PoE splitters are used, providing both power and data connectivity through a single Ethernet cable.

The data from both inverters and reference cells is integrated into PVET via Smartlogger. All information collected by the Smartlogger is stored and connected to the FusionSolar platform. From there, QPV, through the use of PVET, automatically accesses FusionSolar to retrieve the necessary datasets. This ensures seamless and continuous collection of information from both string inverters and EMI devices, providing a reliable data pipeline for further analysis and KPI computation.

The data collected from the irradiance cells and other sensors are stored and processed in a centralized monitoring platform. In Aarhus, this platform is integrated with Smartlogger, a system that centralizes data from various sources, including irradiance data, enabling real-time analysis and operational decision-making as shown in Figure 58. This approach will optimize plant performance, like the Ljubljana plant.

Figure 58: Flow diagram of production data collection and display for Aarhus demonstrator

Figure 59: production and irradiance at Aarhus demonstrator on a sunny day of August 13, 2025.

4.3.4.4 Forest of Dean and Evora demonstrators

Monitoring system configuration in the PV installations of Forest of Dean in the UK is still in progress, since the PV plant has not been completed yet. The monitoring system has been designed and will be installed by a private company: Big Solar Coop, that will share data with the PVET and from there follow the same data flow as other demonstrators.

5 Round robin characterization

The degradation rate of crystalline silicon PV modules is low (below 0.5%/year), but characterizing its actual value is important due to its impact on energy yield and hence profitability over the lifetime of a PV power plant. AURORA project has decided to take advantage of the 5 PV facilities belonging to the five demonstrators to contribute to the characterization of PV power plants operating in different climate conditions as well as with different PV technologies, such as Tunnel Oxide Passivated Contact (TOPCon) cells, Passivated Emitter Rear Contact (PERC) cells, Interdigitated Back Contact (IBC) cells or Hetero Junction Technology (HJT) cells. In addition, monitoring these PV power plants using the systems installed by QPV makes it possible to analyse their productivity, performance ratio (PR) and losses due to shading, solar incidence angles or faults in PV modules.

There are several methods for assessing PV degradation. Traditionally, long-term performance is measured at a constant rate, resulting in a gradual and homogeneous decline in annual performance (in percentage per year) with the assumption of linear performance loss. However, methods considering nonlinear degradation rates reduce estimation uncertainties. These methods require of continuous monitoring of irradiation, temperature, and energy production data.

The 5 AURORA PV power plants will be equipped with irradiance (G_{ef}) and cell temperature (T_C) sensors (both integrated in reference modules) as well as energy meters to measure the energy production.

A monitoring system in each facility will be in charge of recording the following data of the entire installation (equivalent of a SCADA system):

- Operating conditions: effective irradiance (G_{ef}) and cell temperature (T_C) from the reference modules.
- DC operation: Electrical and energy information from a PV array (inverter input), such as DC power (P_{DC}).
- AC operation: Electrical and energy information from an inverter output, such as AC power (P_{AC}).
- Generation Zone operation: Electrical and energy information from the generation zone output (energy meter).

The analysis of the PV degradation rate will be carried out following this procedure:

- During the commissioning of the facility, the PV generator will be subject to an exhaustive inspection within the quality control protocol to detect possible hotspots in cells using thermography (IR thermal cameras), to carry out isolation tests and to perform the I - V measurement of the PV generator in order to characterize its actual nominal power at standard test conditions (STC - 25°C cell temperature and 1000 W/m² of irradiance).
- At the end of the project, or 1 year after the commissioning, and in subsequent measurement campaigns (e.g., 5 years after the commissioning), new measurements of the I - V characteristic will be made in order to quantify the power loss that occurred throughout the operation period. These measurement campaigns will be accompanied by inspections with thermography and detection of defects in PV modules.
- Apart from these measurements, just monitoring the operation parameters defined above, it is possible to calculate the DC power evolution of the PV plant at STC using the following equation:

$$P_{DC,25} = \frac{P_{DC,measured}}{[1 + \gamma \cdot (T_{C,measured} - T_C^*)]}$$

Where, $P_{DC,25}$ is the DC power corrected for temperature, γ is the temperature coefficient of power (extracted from PV modules' datasheet) and T_C^* is the cell temperature at STC ($T_C^* = 25^\circ\text{C}$).

When this corrected DC power is plotted versus the incident irradiance $G_{ef,measured}$, the peak power of the generator (P^*) can be obtained as the linear fit at STC irradiance (G^*). Figure 60 shows the graph obtained with this formula from a 5 kW PV array measured by IES-UPM at its facilities in Campus-Sur in March 2020. The linear relationship between $P_{DC,25}$ and G_{ef} can be observed. It allows to calculate the PV generator peak power (P^*), which is obtained when the

effective irradiance reaches the STC conditions ($G_{ef} = G^*$) in linear fit equation. The Figure 60 shows that the power at STC of the PV array was 4906 W.

Figure 60: $P_{DC,25}$ as a function of G_{ef} in a 5 kW array measured in March 2020 in Madrid.

This power analysis can be carried out every month throughout the lifetime of the PV facilities and, from it, a degradation rate can be obtained as the tilt of the linear fit of the power obtained in the different months.

Moreover, from the data obtained by the monitoring system, the performance ratio (PR) of the PV facility can be calculated. This index defines the relationship between the real energy produced by the PV installation and that which would be produced by a hypothetical ideal installation, whose cells are always kept at a temperature of 25 °C, without being affected by any type of loss. It can be expressed as:

$$PR = \frac{E_{AC}}{\frac{P^*}{G^*} \cdot G_{ef,measured}}$$

The PR will be used as quality index of the PV facilities and can be performed monthly and yearly just considering measurement periods of 1 month or 1 year.

This methodology will be implemented in each one of the five demonstrators, during the 5 years after the execution period of AURORA project, to make a round robin characterization of the PV facilities. The intercomparison of the performance measurements between the five demonstrators will allow to make evaluations about the factors affecting aging and degradation of PV modules, as well as the energy yield of the PV systems, such as climate conditions, the different cells' technologies, the electrical operation conditions, and others.

Clear sky power output forecasting is also set to be implemented, enabling the accurate short-term prediction of PV system output under clear sky conditions. This approach allows for the precise simulation of PV system performance under ideal conditions and demonstrates the effect of ambient temperature and orientation on real-time output. This tool has already been implemented by University of Ljubljana, using a Python-based approach for simulating the expected power output of the AURORA demonstrator installed at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering (Ljubljana), considering module orientation, temperature effects, and meteorological forecasts, as shown in Figure 61.

Figure 61: PV energy forecasting simulation considering clear sky conditions (dashed line) and real time production of the PV power plant (orange area). Real time monitoring available in <https://se.fe.uni-lj.si/>

The following planning is proposed as a basis to implement the round robin characterization:

Period	Action	Results
Commissioning of each of the PV facilities.	Quality control: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I-V measurement of the PV generator to characterize the actual nominal power at standard test conditions STC. • Inspection of possible hotspots in cells and other defects. • Isolation tests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial PV generator peak power (P^*). • Possible defects.
1 year after the commissioning.	2 nd quality control.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV generator peak power (P^*) after 1 year. • Power loss measurement. • Possible defects.
5 years after the commissioning.	3 rd quality control.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV generator peak power (P^*) after 5 years. • Power loss measurement. • Possible defects.
Throughout the operation phase since the commissioning (Monthly reports).	Data recorded by the monitoring system: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective irradiance (G_{ef}) and cell temperature (T_c) from the reference modules. • DC power (P_{DC}). • AC power (P_{AC}). • LV energy generation (E_{AC}). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly and yearly DC power corrected in temperature ($P_{DC,25}$). • Monthly and yearly PR index. • Power loss characterization.

Table 15: Round robin planning

5.1 Results

Expected results at the end of the project and 5 years after the commissioning should match with power loss ratios reported in specialized literature about Si-c technology. However, the implementation of new PV technologies in the different demonstrators (TOPcon, PERC, IBC and HJT cells) working at different meteorological conditions, can lead to results significantly different from what estimated. Actually, since PV demonstrators aim to integrate new PV technologies, the assessment of their performance constitutes one of the outputs of AURORA.

The results obtained from the five demosites will reveal differences in performance between different photovoltaic technologies at different location. These results will still be attainable within the project duration. As currently predicted, close to one year of monitoring data will also be available before the end of the project. This data will give the first insights into initial degradation factors with respect to the location of the demosites. Since the data will be aggregated in a single database, it will provide an excellent source of data for long term degradation, which will be evaluated in years after the end of the project.

6 Replication

6.1 Introduction

Apart from establishing RECs at five demo sites, the goals of the Aurora project were to develop approaches to establish RECs and enable their replication. The benefit of all the encountered barriers is that instead of one solution, in the Aurora project we developed several solutions.

It must be noted, that each concept is adapted to national legislation and social acceptance in different countries. The EU decree that Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) only instruct member states to transfer this term into national legislation, but it does not prescribe exactly how. As a result, the legal conditions for RECs depends on the implementation of REC in national legislation and are thus different in different member states. National legislations may also have different exceptions (e.g. prosumer via third party in Denmark), which may enable or make it easier or more difficult to establish a REC. Also, procedures for registering a new legal entity, legal requirements for PV power plant installation, grid connection procedures etc. are different in different countries, and may also be different in different areas of the countries and at different distribution system operators. This means that the approaches developed within Aurora can be used as guidelines on how to establish RECs but national and local legislation together with legal entity guidelines are what finally defines the path of individual REC.

While the developed approaches are all based around photovoltaic power plants, as they only require a free roof, they can also be replicated with different types of power plant depending on the energy source available at given location, such as wind, hydro, geothermal or cogeneration.

The approaches developed with the Aurora can be summarized in three classes:

- REC as a new independent cooperative
- REC under existing legal entity
- Virtual REC

In this chapter we highlight the most important points of these three classes and point the reader to corresponding chapters of this deliverable and other documents, where different approaches are described in detail. We also provide information on already realised replications as well as on replications that are already in progress or foreseen.

6.2 REC as a new independent cooperative

This is an approach initially envisaged in the Aurora project. A new independent cooperative is established. The crowdfunding process includes investors in the ownership structure of the cooperative and gives them voting rights. This approach was carried out for a demonstrator site in Aarhus, Denmark. The participation of the Aarhus University as an electricity consumer is possible due to prosumer via third party legislation unique to Denmark. More information can be found in:

- Aurora project, deliverable 3.3 (this document), section 3.4 Demonstrator Site – Aarhus, Denmark, page 52
- Marta Victoria et al, “Challenges and strategies for establishing a rooftop photovoltaic system crowdsourced by students and employees at Aarhus University”, 2024 IEEE 52nd Photovoltaic Specialist Conference (PVSC), DOI: 10.1109/PVSC57443.2024.10748869
- <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/au-main/>
- <https://www.uef.dk/home>

6.3 REC under existing legal entity

In this approach an existing legal entity is a legal vehicle, under which the Renewable Energy Community is formed and enables crowdfunding and installation of PV power plant, including carbon emission offset and economical return. The Aurora energy community exists separately (legally formally or informally) and is the background driving force that enables, accelerates and pushes the execution of the REC. Depending on implementation, crowdfunding investors either lend money as a loan and receive back the principal with interest, or they buy shares and enter the ownership structure of the REC. This approach was implemented in Madrid and Forest of Dean, and proposed in Evora.

6.3.1 Colegio Centro Cultural Palomeras primary school cooperative

In Madrid, the UPM community, the Campus Sur Platform worked together with external energy advisor Ecooo proposed a PV facility on a nearby private primary school, which is legally organized as a cooperative. The project evolved into an installation of PV power plant and two heat pumps. The crowdfunding was organized as a loan to the CCCP. More information can be found in:

- Aurora project, deliverable 3.3 (this document), section 3.1 Demonstrator Site – Madrid, Spain, page: 14
- <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/um-main/>

6.3.2 Forest of Dean District Council and Big Solar Co-op

In the Forest of Dean District council, the Forest Community Energy together with existing cooperative Big Solar Co-op designed a two-phase project to install PV facilities on the local swimming pool and on the local school. The crowdfunding process is organized as buying shares of the Big Solar Co-op cooperative. By doing so investors enter ownership structure of Big Solar Co-op and they also get a voting right. More information can be found in:

- Aurora project, deliverable 3.3 (this document), section 3.5 Demonstrator Site – Forest of Dean, United Kingdom, page:61
- <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/fod-home/>

6.3.3 The Red Cross model

In Evora, the team in Évora developed a business plan, where Renewable Energy Communities would be created under the coverage of the local Red Cross delegations. Red Cross buildings would host a PV facility. The investors would be given retribution to the free physical card (cartão Dá), while a part of revenue would be directed towards fighting energy poverty of the vulnerable individuals. This attempt was not realized in the scope of Aurora because the communication with the Red Cross Evora stalled. However, we believe that it is still a feasible approach with significant potential, especially involving vulnerable collectives, therefore we report on it and promote it further. More information can be found in:

- Aurora project, deliverable 3.3 (this document), section 3.2.3 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, Attempt 2 – REC within the Red Cross – failed, page 25
- <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/eu-main/>

6.4 Virtual Energy Community

The virtual approach to Energy Community is the simplest one because it does not include crowdfunding. That is also the main drawback of this approach as it lacks this part of involvement of the community.

Despite this, it was the only feasible approach in Ljubljana. The community was formed as Student Energy Club and takes care for communication, education and raising awareness. The PV installation was funded by the University of Ljubljana member, the Faculty of Electrical engineering, which also self-consumes the produced electricity. More information can be found in:

- Aurora project, deliverable 3.3 (this document), section 3.3 Demonstrator Site – Ljubljana, Slovenia, page: 32
- <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/ul-main/>
- <https://www.s3k.si>

The virtual approach was finally also adopted in Evora as a mitigation strategy due to lost time developing the Red Cross model. The informal community was formed as a Sustainable Action Group. More information can be found in:

- Aurora project, deliverable 3.3 (this document), section 3.2.5 Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, Virtual approach with existing power plant – mitigation measure, page 29
- <https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/eu-main/>

6.5 Impossible attempts

In the beginning of the project the initial idea of most university partners was to realize Renewable Energy Community within the universities themselves, however that turned out to be impossible due to several reasons:

- Universities do not qualify into any of legal terms listed under possible energy community membership: “Natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises and microenterprises, ...”,
- Universities may not have financial products offering interest or payments resulting from capital income to participants or having outgoing cash flows,
- University administrations are very conservative and employees are not comfortable taking any legal risks.

Although the last reason is not legal it is important never the less, since for the first two reasons there were several legal debates, which may have turned out differently should the legal side of the universities be more motivated.

A path also investigated was via associations or foundations. However, associations require assembly-based decision-making and are exclusively private, limiting public institution involvement and control. The foundations are more flexible and compatible with public entities, but, based on EU guidance, universities have ruled out creating ad hoc foundations for project’s objectives, and using existing foundations is not viable because they may not receive private funding.

6.6 Realized replications

Although the Aurora facilities in the Forest of Dean were not yet realized, the Forest Community Energy was very active in communicating their efforts and have thus attracted two replication opportunities that have been completed before the Aurora facilities.

Firstly, The Speech House Hotel has an installation of around 150 solar panels on the more modern additions to the original buildings will help to underpin the green policy of the business. Local installer Nimbus Solar completed the installation, using ethical and sustainable Meyer Burger solar PV panels in December 2024. AURORA Forest of Dean and Forest Community Energy are delighted with this progress and believe the unique business model is a win win for the hotel and the environment. A great example of steps taken on the net zero journey and a demonstrator project to celebrate.

Secondly, Forest Community Energy, in collaboration with Gloucestershire Community Energy Ltd. and Gwent Energy CIC have supported the Sling Community Hub to get solar PV installed in June 2025 – saving them money and helping them to do their bit to tackle climate change. The Sling Community Hub is a much loved hub which sits at the heart of the local community. They cater for a variety of people through their activities from toddler groups to cafes for older residents to their quizzes and pub nights. The community hub also hosted the thermal imaging loan service pilot that AURORA ran in the winter of 2024. 39 solar photovoltaic (PV) panels have been installed by Gwent Energy CIC on the roof to generate electricity for use in the building in the day. A battery was also installed to store any surplus electricity not used so it can be used in the evenings to power the bar and beer coolers for example. Gloucestershire Community Energy Ltd who are funding this installation have been able to do this through their community ownership model – this means that local residents can invest to own part of the installation. The share offer is open until 31st August 2025, and investment is a minimum of £250 and up to £5,000 with a projected 3.5% annual return on investment.

This rapid development of two relatively simple facilities within private or small public entities illustrates that the public sector is not incentivised enough to undertake the energy transition with the level of urgency and efficiency required.

6.7 Replications in progress

Replications in progress or foreseen replicators are in contact with Aurora partners, who provide full support.

In Denmark, we learnt that the new campus of **Aarhus University (Campus 2.0)** plans to install solar panels on the new buildings, and a community-owned installation such as demonstrated in AURORA can be a solution for consideration. In addition, other public institutions such as libraries and hospitals would be potential replicators. In the process of developing their own community energy scheme, **University College Dublin** in Ireland becomes interested in the approach taken by AURORA partners, particularly the framework adopted in Aarhus. We have already conducted online meetings and shared materials with them between project AURORA and UC Dublin. In Aarhus, we are seeing that the **Aarhus Wind Cooperative** is developing their project with the energy cooperative model. Another emerging energy community is Sol over Brabrand, where rooftop solar is considered for the community.

At UPM, **The Fuhem Foundation** (<https://www.fuhem.es>) showed interest to replicate the Aurora project with their facilities. They asked for information about legal, technical and economic aspects of the projects.

In Portugal the first replication opportunity already lies within the **Red Cross Portugal**. They have 170 delegations across the country and are looking closely to the Renewable Energy Community in Évora. In the past we have evaluated commercial offers to a Red Cross delegation in the Algarve and they are seeking the opportunity to replicate, considering that they will have their own “living lab”.

The team in Évora is making efforts to start registering a second collective self-consumption energy community in its **campus in the outskirts of Évora**, in which the research group has several PV facilities (100 kW E-W tracking, 6 white BIPV modules, 3.3 kW amorphous old PV plant, is developing a 65 kW AgriPV system and throughout next year a new AgriPV plant of circa 200 kW will be developed) together with existing PV plants from the university with 32 kW.

Associação de Moradores e Cidadãos Malagueira Viva e Vivida, resident’s association in Évora reached out to UEvora, seeking support on how to develop a REC for their residents considering that that neighbourhood comprises social housing and people in vulnerable conditions. The team supported them in the application for a funding of 100k€ (125k€ funded at 80%, in each the additional 20% contribution comes from university of Évora PM dedication to the development of the project) for the acquisition of PV generation and Energy Storage so that a REC can be created for the neighbourhood. The call was funded by a EDP Foundation and is dedicated to creating social impact through energy innovation. The proposal has passed the first stage in July 2025, and the second stage of evaluation has to be submitted by the end of November 2025.

They are also taking part in another project for the establishment of civic and municipal roadmaps for a just energy transition in the **municipalities of Beira Litoral** (Central region of Portugal, north of Alentejo) in which the Red Cross approach has been presented and real interest is being shown.

UEvora takes part in the Life project JALON, together with UPM, which is setting up a large-scale (2500 km²) renewable energy community in the **region of Calatayud** (Zaragoza, Spain). Under the scope of its responsibilities, UEvora has created a plan to replicate the experience in the region and is engaging in contacts for that purpose, using as a selling point the Red Cross approach.

Additionally, it was identified the opening of a future financing call for the Alentejo for the setting up of Renewable Energy Communities to be led by local authorities. The team in Évora is engaging with local authorities seeking to provide support for the implementation of new Renewable Energy Communities with the support of knowledge developed in AURORA and JALON projects, seeking to intertwine approaches.

The learning of key project management tasks, legal requirements, planning permission and permit approval requirements is being applied to the replication opportunities. Knowledge of the key challenges, barriers and mistakes from the Aurora installations mean that the replicators can fast track subsequent installations and apply our model more effectively and accurately.

7 Dissemination and communication activities

Although dissemination and communication activities are organized and monitored by WP5, we have put emphasis to disseminate and communicate developments within WP3 as well. This has been done on two levels.

The first level addresses wider audience, researchers, replicators, citizen scientist and policy makers. The paper published in Solar RRL represents overall findings of the project on policy related matters:

- Ana Belen Cristóbal et al., “Igniting University Communities: Building Strategies that Empower an Energy Transition through Solar Energy Communities,” Solar RRL, vol. 7, no. 24, p. 2300498, 2023, doi: 10.1002/solr.202300498.

Another paper discusses the social aspect of energy communities to act as centres for systemic transformation toward energy transition:

- Ana Belen Cristóbal et al., “Delving into the modelling and operation of energy communities as epicentres for systemic transformations,” Univ Access Inf Soc, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10209-023-01056-0.

The lessons learned during establishment of REC in Aarhus were published in a paper in Progress in Photovoltaics:

- Marta Victoria et al., “Lessons Learned From Establishing a Rooftop Photovoltaic System Crowdsourced by Students and Employees at Aarhus University”, Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications, Jun. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.70009>

We were also present at several conferences where we presented our results and challenges, while simultaneously we encourage widespread use of the Aurora energy tracker app as well as we identified Aurora ambassadors:

- Ana Belen Cristóbal et al., “Unlocking the Potential of Photovoltaic Energy Communities in the Public Sector: Action for the PV Community,” 40th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition 2023, pp. 020501-1–6, 22.09 2023, doi: 10.4229/EUPVSEC2023/5DO.10.1.
- Matevž Bokalič et al., “A Rationale to Foster the Role of Energy Communities in Creating Inclusive Social Hubs for Citizen Science in Energy Aspects,” presented at the BEHAVE 2023 - The 7th European Conference on Behaviour Change For Energy Efficiency, Maastricht, The Netherlands, 2023.
- Marta Victoria et al, “Challenges and strategies for establishing a rooftop photovoltaic system crowdsourced by students and employees at Aarhus University”, 2024 IEEE 52nd Photovoltaic Specialist Conference (PVSC), DOI: 10.1109/PVSC57443.2024.10748869
- Matevž Bokalič et al., “Challenges of Energy Communities at Universities – A Virtual Approach”, 41st European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, EU PVSEC 2024, pp 020557-001, Vienna, Austria.
- Marta Victoria et al, “Challenges and Strategies for Establishing a Rooftop Photovoltaic System Crowdsourced by Students and Employees at a University”, 41st European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, EU PVSEC 2024, Vienna, Austria
- CIES'2024 XIX Iberian Congress and XV Ibero-American Solar Energy Congress
 - Ana Belen (AURORA Coordinator) - a Keynote speech on Renewable Energy Communities
 - Rica, H., et al., “Comunidade de Energia Renovável do Centro Humanitário de Évora da Cruz Vermelha de Portugal”
 - Bunge, L., et al., “Electricidade solar para auto-consumo em aplicações móveis”

Furthermore, we are planning to join the following events:

- Matevž Bokalič et al., "Comparative study of energy yield in PV systems using different module technologies and inverter configurations ", to be presented at 42nd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, EU PVSEC 2025, Bilbao, Spain

A master degree thesis was successfully defended on the topic of simulation of the technical and economic management of the collective self-consumption and Red Cross Scenarios at the University of Evora:

- Henrique Rica, "Desenvolvimento de um modelo de simulação da gestão técnica e económica de Comunidades de Energia Renovável para a Universidade de Évora e para o Centro Humanitário de Évora da Cruz Vermelha Portuguesa", Master Degree in Solar Energy Engineering at University of Evora

The second level are numerous local dissemination efforts at each demo site, which are described separately at corresponding subsection of the demo sites:

- 3.1.5 at Demonstrator Site – Madrid, Spain, page 19
- 3.2.6 at Demonstrator Site – Évora, Portugal, page 30
- 3.3.5 at Demonstrator Site – Ljubljana, Slovenia, page 49
- 3.4.5 at Demonstrator Site – Aarhus, Denmark, page 58
- 3.5.5 at Demonstrator Site – Forest of Dean, United Kingdom, page 66

8 Conclusion

Since the beginning of the AURORA project WP3 beneficiaries screened their existing communities and investigated options to form renewable energy communities and install demonstrator photovoltaic power plants. The best options were gathered together in the form of the business models that are presented deliverable D3.1.

During the implementation of the business models there was a lot of communication with various third parties involved in the process, with administrations and decision-making bodies of the universities while the whole process had to be kept within the legal and structural limitations. The process was significantly more complicated than initially planned with many obstacles that had to be solved. These consequently delayed the implementation of renewable energy communities and the installation of the power plants. Simultaneously the partners were forced to change and adapt initial business plans by developing innovative approaches to circumvent these obstacles. This results in a variety of different solutions presented herein.

AU team was able to keep the original proposed business plan, established REC based on new independent cooperative, and crowdfunded the PV installation that in part provides electricity to Aarhus University. UPM team had to change their initial business model several times, because it was rejected by their administration due to legal incompatibility. They formed an informal community Campus Sur Platform, which worked together with external energy advisor Ecooo to crowdfund a project with PV facility and two heat pumps on a nearby private primary school, which is legally organized as a cooperative. Despite initially positive feedback from previous administration at UEvora, the business plan to form REC legally under University was rejected by the new administration. They proposed a new business plan to implement REC via local Red Cross delegation. Despite significant effort invested in designing and planning, the approach finally stalled. The two unsuccessful attempts required precious time, therefore they finally activated a mitigation approach, where they formed an informal Sustainable Action Group who leveraged an existing PV power plant for demonstration purposes, essentially following a virtual approach developed earlier at UL. At UL a virtual approach was already proposed in D3.1 due to legal limitations. A community was formed informally as a Student Energy Club. During implementation, they encountered significant problems due to structure of the roof, erroneous initial static assessment and problematic anchoring of the PVPP, which resulted in termination of the first staged approach. They then proceeded with the public tender approach, which was successful. to cover all available roofs. The tender was successful and the contract was signed. Currently they are waiting for grid permits. In FoDDC, due to different social environment, REC implementation had to be correctly presented to the community. They will establish REC on local leisure centre and school under legal coverage of the developer Big Solar Co-op. They are currently waiting signatures of last legal documents required before installation.

In conclusion, all demonstrators were successfully established, albeit none followed exactly the initial plan, where the universities would legally enable crowdfunding of the PV installations. During the process, we have learned that legally universities are defined such that they either do not qualify into any of legal terms listed under possible energy community membership: “Natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises and microenterprises, ...”, nor may they have financial products offering interest or payments resulting from capital income to participants or having outgoing cash flows. These two facts make it virtually impossible for a university to form a REC. This is further reinforced by the fact that administrations bodies of large public institutions are not keen to take legal risk and venture into the unknown field of RECs. While this is understandable from personal point of view of employees, this also makes it significantly more difficult if not impossible for research teams and also possible replicators to establish RECs. This shows that the reward for mitigating climate change is not large enough to incentive REC establishment compared to relatively small (financial) gains. This could be improved by two things, one is better education with raised awareness of the problem, while the other is legislation that would require and encourage adoptions of RECs on universities and other public institutions.

